

**LIVED EXPERIENCES ON WELLBEING OF UNIVERSITY
TEACHERS IN THE NEW NORMAL: BASIS FOR
PSYCHOSOCIAL SUPPORT SERVICES**

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Lived Experiences on Wellbeing of University Teachers in the New Normal: Basis For Psychosocial Support Services

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has compelled teachers to adapt to numerous changes both before and during the transition back to in-person learning, leading to reduced attention on their well-being. This study employed a qualitative phenomenological approach to explore the lived experiences of university teachers in Pampanga, Philippines, specifically focusing on their personal perspectives, challenges, and coping mechanisms for maintaining well-being in the New Normal. The study utilized the University of Maryland's eight dimensions of well-being and Dunn's Wheel of Wellness as models. Through purposive sampling, teachers experiencing high stress and low to moderate well-being were identified using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) and the BBC-Wellbeing Scale. Seven participants underwent in-depth interviews, with qualitative data collected, organized, and analyzed through thematic analysis. To ensure data integrity, validation was obtained from participants and experts. The findings revealed that teachers had positive perceptions of their vocational, emotional, spiritual, social, intellectual, and environmental well-being, but negative perceptions of their financial and physical well-being. External challenges were noted in vocational and environmental aspects, while other dimensions faced internal challenges. Interestingly, teachers used problem-solving coping mechanisms for all well-being challenges except emotional well-being. Challenges were categorized into five areas for improvement: Career Development, Financial Literacy, Positive Emotions, Meaningful Connections, and Physical Health and Safety. These areas formed the basis for proposed Psychosocial Support Services for teachers. The study's results and findings offer valuable insights for the practice of Guidance and Counseling for school professionals.

Keywords: *wellbeing, psychosocial support, new normal, university teachers, guidance and counseling*

Introduction

Well-being is defined as the overall quality of an individual's life (Diener et al., 2002). It encompasses multiple interconnected domains such as physical, intellectual, emotional, social, spiritual, vocational, financial, and environmental (University of Maryland, 2022). COVID-19 created rapid change as the worldwide spread led to multiple crises, adversely affecting people's well-being. In the wake of a crisis, societies and economies have undergone significant changes that redefined their operations and behaviors. These various changes are called "new normal" which refers to a new way of functioning that reflects the lessons learned and adaptations made in response to the COVID crisis (World Economic Forum, 2020). School Communities were one of those sectors severely affected.

In addition, we have seen an emerging picture of how students grappled with the effects of a pandemic on their holistic health and how schools continue to mitigate the pandemic-associated reports of mental illnesses, cases of dropouts, poor socialization, and many others (United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization, 2020). Social isolation, rapid changes, fear of infection, and the economic consequences of the pandemic were identified as significant stressors directly affecting well-being (Xiong et al., 2020). In contrast, there is less attention given to teachers' well-being, despite their efforts in supporting the recovery process of the students. Few research explored the quality of well-being of teachers during this crisis. Some focused on specific psychosocial and emotional effects of pandemic to teachers, for instance, Cohen-Fraade and Donahue (2022) and Santamaría et al. (2021), similarly found increasing symptoms of anxiety and depression which were associated with the stresses of teaching in the first year of the pandemic. This cumulative high percentage of symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression since March 2020 comes from excessive workload, lack of clear guidelines, and lack of staff and resources. The stress on learning and using education technologies to carry out flexible pedagogies, or the "technostress" are major sources of burnout among primary and secondary education teachers (Estrada-Muñoz et al., 2021). Also, trouble with sleeping and stress exhibited their neutrality in returning to stressful experiences, making them vulnerable to other well-being concerns (Jimenez, 2021). Significantly, researchers agreed that female teachers are found vulnerable among the population.

Prevention and wellness are two of the goals of counseling and the rationale for all the services and activities offered in guidance and counseling. It must integrate wellness-based strategies that support and optimize the client's holistic well-being (Long et al., 2022). Thus, addressing teachers' experiences of adjustment from crises and pandemic-related issues through mental health support and interventions is needed, to promote conducive working conditions and self-efficacy to manage the pandemic challenges encountered inside and outside the school, for there is no learning recovery without prepared, appreciated, and empowered teachers (World Economic Forum, 2022).

As restrictions are lifted, after 3 years of the COVID-19 pandemic, schools and universities in Pampanga, Philippines are now allowed to conduct one full week of face-to-face classes. This transition from virtual or remote teaching to face-to-face classes in universities, not only potentially challenged the well-being of students but most greatly of teachers who are the frontliners of these educational

changes. Teachers may need to re-learn classroom dynamics, adapt teaching materials, and consider the mental health and well-being of students who may have experienced anxiety or stress during the pandemic. Aside from several mental and physical health concerns, the economic crisis has also affected the institution's stability as the pandemic significantly impacted teachers' preference for higher-paying state-owned schools. While schools are preparing for their facilities, curriculum, and accreditations, there is a need to evaluate and prepare teachers' well-being and assess how these current adjustments influence them to enhance their resilience and self-efficacy.

Few studies and literature showed insufficient emphasis on the quality of well-being of university teachers in the new normal setup. Although well-being of teachers is crucial during the transition to full face-to-face instruction, there is lesser attention on the subjective well-being of teachers particularly assessing the lived experiences of teachers on the eight dimensions of well-being, their physical, intellectual, emotional, social, spiritual, vocational, financial, and environmental well-being, which this study aimed to describe. Since teacher's well-being was found crucial to learning outcomes, evidence-based psychosocial support services are significant in supporting teachers' overall well-being while navigating the challenges of this shift from remote learning to face-to-face learning. According to the American Psychological Association (APA), Psychosocial support services are mental health services that encompass a wide range of support provided by professionals to help individuals facing serious challenges brought on by a crisis. These services can include counseling, education, group support, spiritual guidance, and other forms of assistance. They can be offered by various professionals, including psychologists, counselors, social workers, and pastoral counselors. Designing these services based on the quality of teachers' well-being is the major contribution of the study in guidance and counseling specifically during the recovery of teachers and the educational systems in post-pandemic education. Addressing the gap between the quality of well-being of teachers during a remote learning environment and the shift to pure in-person learning can lead to a more comprehensive understanding and recommendations to the Universities to support the basic needs of teachers, to improve their well-being, then eventually their self-efficacy and resilience in this evolving educational landscape.

In this study, the researcher aims to contribute to Psychology and Education by describing and understanding the subjective experiences and perceptions of university teachers on their well-being specifically the eight dimension of well-being, the challenges they encountered, the coping mechanisms employed in navigating these challenges which will serve as a framework for the proposed psychosocial support services tailored to the specific needs of University Teachers in this new normal crisis.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to explore the lived experiences of University Teachers in Pampanga on wellbeing in the new normal. Specifically, it intended to achieve the following objectives:

1. To describe and analyze the lived experiences of University Teachers as to their Personal view on wellbeing, challenges, and coping mechanisms on the following components:
 - 1.1 vocational;
 - 1.2 financial;
 - 1.3 emotional;
 - 1.4 spiritual;
 - 1.5 social;
 - 1.6 intellectual;
 - 1.7 physical; and
 - 1.8 environmental.
2. To propose Psychosocial Support Services (PSSS) for teachers based on the findings.
3. To identify the implication of the study to guidance and counseling.

Literature Review

Wellbeing and Wellness

The current research considers well-being as a multidimensional concept, with various theories and models emphasizing its different aspects. Over the years, these facets have been closely examined to define an individual's well-being. The World Health Organization, in 1948, introduced well-being as extending beyond just the absence of illness, encompassing numerous dimensions of human health. This includes positive mental health factors, as outlined in the mental health model proposed by Keyes, C. L. M. (2005), which comprises emotional well-being, psychological well-being, and social well-being.

Furthermore, the book "Well-being: The Foundations of Hedonic Psychology" by Kahneman, D., Diener, E., & Schwarz, N. (Eds., 1999) discusses the concept of hedonic well-being, which focuses on the pursuit of pleasure and happiness. Diener, E., Lucas, R.E., & Oishi, S. (2002) suggest that individuals seek to maximize happiness and minimize suffering within this perspective by assessing factors such as life satisfaction and positive affect. Additionally, they found a significant connection between personality traits like extraversion and neuroticism and an individual's subjective well-being.

Moreover, another perspective on well-being is eudaimonic well-being, which emphasizes the pursuit of meaning and self-

actualization. Waterman, A. S. (1993) discovered that prioritizing personal growth and self-expression leads to greater overall well-being. This perspective suggests that a sense of purpose and self-discovery significantly contribute to subjective well-being and psychological wellness. In contemporary psychology, Martin Seligman (2011) introduced the PERMA model, which identifies five essential elements for cultivating well-being: positive emotions, engagement, positive relationships, meaning, and achievement. Balancing these elements in life can lead to higher levels of well-being and overall flourishing.

While wellness is sometimes used interchangeably with well-being, it is important to note that they are related but distinct concepts. Wellness, as defined by Dunn (1959), encompasses physical, mental, and social well-being, going beyond the mere absence of disease. The American Psychiatric Association (dictionary.apa.org) on the other hand defined Wellness as ways of actively pursuing a state of well-being through various aspects of one's life, such as control over biology, environment, lifestyle, and health care management. Roscoe (2009) argued that wellness is not synonymous with well-being, but rather influences it, because wellness is the sum of the positive steps taken to achieve well-being. As cited by Albrecht (2014), wellness is defined as the integration of the whole person - the body, mind, and spirit with wellness, described as different spiritual, cognitive, emotional, environmental, and physical aspects. The current study adopted the Eight Dimensions of Wellness namely, physical, emotional, social, intellectual, environmental, spiritual, vocational, and financial well-being. As included in the conceptual framework for a holistic approach to balance life and health proposed in the article of Kaslly (2023) and University of Maryland (2022) on well-being. It is important to consider the requirement for Psychosocial support services that address these eight dimensions of well-being, as society shifts to entirely face-to-face interactions. These programs can support people in readjusting to face-to-face interactions and helping them maintain a healthy balance in all aspects of their lives.

Teacher Wellbeing amidst COVID-19 pandemic

Teacher well-being is essential in education as it not only prevents negative emotions and stress but also promotes positive emotions and personal and professional growth (Forster, M., Kuhbandner, C., & Hilbert, S., 2022). Positive teacher well-being positively impacts students' learning and development, leading to higher academic achievements, improved student well-being, enhanced teaching quality, and increased professional motivation. This helps teachers find reward in their profession, preventing burnout and fostering meaningful work.

Teachers' sense of fulfillment in teaching, especially during the pandemic, is crucial (Pabillore et al., 2020). Factors such as workplace relationships, school leadership, and personal well-being contribute to teachers' occupational well-being. Workload, inadequate salary, lack of support from school administration, and student behavior issues are key stressors for teachers, particularly female teachers and those with higher educational attainment. The study by Collie et al. (2021) on teachers' well-being during the COVID-19 surge found increased levels of burnout, anxiety, and depression due to the rapid shift to online teaching, increased workload, concerns for students' well-being, and teachers' health. Emotional well-being, defined as one's ability to regulate emotions, form positive connections, and make responsible decisions amid life's challenges, is crucial in establishing healthy relationships (Weare, K., 2015). Emotional intelligence, resilience, empathy, and self-efficacy play vital roles in regulating emotions, forming and maintaining relationships, and making effective decisions (Durlak et al., 2011).

Environmental wellness is about maintaining a harmonious relationship with our surroundings, including conserving energy, supporting eco-friendly practices, and appreciating nature (University of Maryland, 2022). The quality of the environment teachers work in directly impacts their overall well-being, with access to greenspace positively influencing mental health (White et al., 2013). Interacting with natural surroundings has positive effects on mental well-being, leading to stress reduction, enhanced mood, increased physical activity, social interaction, and cognitive restoration. Addressing various aspects of well-being, including physical, social, vocational, environmental, intellectual, spiritual, and emotional dimensions, is crucial for teachers' health, happiness, and satisfaction. This holistic approach contributes to their overall well-being and professional development, emphasizing the importance of implementing programs to support teachers in maintaining and improving their well-being. In summary, prioritizing teacher well-being, fostering positive workplace relationships, addressing stress factors, promoting emotional and environmental wellness, and implementing holistic well-being programs are essential in supporting teachers' overall health and professional success.

Teacher's coping with COVID-19 challenges

Lived experiences of individuals during the COVID-19 pandemic have been studied extensively over the past few years, with a focus on well-being and coping strategies. Charles R. Synder's (1999) theory of coping highlights the individual's response to both positive and negative external events, emphasizing the importance of conscious decision-making and personal awareness in managing stressful situations. This can be related to the experience of teachers on pandemic that challenged their adaptation to various changes on personal, social, professional and environmental aspects. Health Psychology by Taylor (2011) offers practices to develop coping mechanisms, such as maintaining a positive emotional state, fostering optimism, practicing psychological control, utilizing cognitive-behavioral techniques, and relaxation methods. Emotional intelligence, as proposed by Peter Salovey et al. (1999), plays a significant role in coping, starting from basic emotional skills to deeper emotional knowledge. Aulén et al. (2021) examined coping strategies among teachers using a person-oriented approach and identified four coping profiles: Low-coping users, Problem-focused-coping users, High-coping users, and Emotion-focused-coping users. The study found that teachers with high levels of emotion-focused coping and low problem-focused coping experienced more stress and negative outcomes compared to other profiles.

Local studies have investigated coping mechanisms used by teachers in response to work-related stress. Teachers often rely on problem-oriented strategies, social support, and positive coping mechanisms when faced with challenges. Adapting to the demands of pandemic education, such as providing quality resources and supporting work-life balance, is crucial for teachers' well-being (Dotimas, 2022; Palomique, 2023). Studies also emphasize the importance of psychosocial support for teachers, recognizing the impact of stress on their mental health and workplace performance (Jimenez, 2021; Rilveria, 2018). Creating supportive work environments, promoting resilience, and fostering psychological need satisfaction are key factors in enhancing teachers' adjustment to work and overall well-being (Desrumaux et al., 2023; Jimenez, 2021). In conclusion, understanding and applying effective coping strategies are essential for individuals, especially teachers, to navigate challenges and maintain well-being during difficult times like the COVID-19 pandemic. Implementing psychosocial support services, promoting resilience, and creating supportive work environments are crucial steps in ensuring the mental health and professional success of educators.

Psychosocial support services for teachers

The Inter-agency Network for Education in Emergencies (2018) defined Psychosocial support (PSS) as a form of love, care, and protection that helps improve a person's mental, emotional, and spiritual well-being, as well as their social and cultural connections. It is crucial for individual, family, and community resilience and overall thriving. Effective support draws on the strengths of the individual and their community and should be consistently provided through various sources such as home, school, friends, and local services. Similarly, according to UNICEF (2019), mental health and psychosocial support encompass local or outside support and resources that aim to protect or promote psychosocial well-being and/or prevent or treat mental health conditions. These services can be delivered by a variety of professionals, including psychologists, social workers, pastoral counselors, and others (APA, 2024).

While acknowledging the stressful nature of the teaching profession that may lead to burnout, it is crucial to prioritize the safety and well-being of students while also addressing the well-being of teachers. Psychosocial support for teachers plays a key role in their well-being and effectiveness within the school environment, yet few interventions for teachers were available and were not given enough attention. Effective coping strategies, support from colleagues, and a positive school environment can assist teachers in managing stress and thriving in their profession. Primary school teachers, in particular, are under significant stress, indicating the need for further research to explore ways to enhance their workload and well-being. It is important to recognize that teachers' well-being goes beyond the absence of illness and encompasses their ability to thrive in the workplace. Dealing with stressors such as violence or aggressive behavior in schools requires supportive leadership and positive relationships with colleagues to foster resilience. Factors like emotional intelligence and training can aid in preventing burnout. However, systemic changes within the educational system may be necessary to establish a sustainable and supportive work environment for teachers. Simply focusing on individual factors without addressing broader structural issues may not lead to lasting improvements in teacher well-being (Benevene et al., 2020). Teachers and other education support professionals have reported feeling frustrated and lacking social and emotional learning (SEL) support in their daily work, as identified in a study by Naples et al (2022). This is attributed to a lack of resources and clarity regarding job roles during the pandemic. A wide range of emotions, including frustration, happiness, joy, anxiety, and stress, were identified among educators. There is a desire for appreciation, value, and respect in addressing these challenges. Developing strategies to regulate emotions and reflect on feelings can assist teachers in overcoming these obstacles. The utilization of self-regulation strategies and support for social-emotional learning may vary based on school level and professional role. Therefore, supporting job satisfaction and career development for teachers is crucial in the provision of psychosocial support services within schools.

Psychosocial support also plays a vital role in addressing health concerns. A meta-analysis conducted by Smith et al. (2021), focusing on 106 randomized controlled trials, suggests that psychosocial support interventions can enhance patient survival in medical settings. Interventions emphasizing health behaviors were deemed more effective than those focusing on emotional or social outcomes. Studies have consistently demonstrated the significant impact of social relationships on health outcomes. Loneliness and social isolation are associated with an increased risk of mortality, while social support can positively impact physical health, adherence to treatment, physical activity, and sleep quality. Furthermore, social relationships have been linked to reduced levels of inflammation and gene expression associated with cancer. These findings emphasize the importance of social integration and support in promoting overall health and well-being.

During the pandemic, survivors of COVID-19 may experience symptoms of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), particularly if they had severe and prolonged infections and were isolated from their families (Ellyamurti & Hartanti, 2023). These survivors may benefit from psychosocial support to help them cope with feelings of loneliness and negative emotions. Research by Garriott et al. (2023) suggests that the Emotional and Stress Management Intervention (ESMI) developed by Action Against Hunger can be effective in reducing distress and increasing social support among COVID-19 survivors in Liberia, Sierra Leone, and Ivory Coast.

Additionally, stress management practices, such as Mindfulness-Based Interventions (MBIs), have been found beneficial for promoting teacher well-being (Hepburn et al., 2021). Studies have shown that MBIs can reduce perceived stress, increase attention awareness, and improve subjective well-being among educators. Implementing programs like DeStress Monday at School, an online mindfulness program for teachers, can also be beneficial in improving teachers' health and wellness outcomes during challenging times like the COVID-19 pandemic (Mendelson et al., 2023). Moreover, incorporating positive psychology concepts into psychosocial support services is crucial for promoting teacher well-being. Models such as sustainable well-being literacy, which focus on fostering positive

relationships and building hope among teachers, can be effective in enhancing teacher efficacy and optimism (Ronen & Kerret, 2020). Emphasizing constructive emotions like gratitude, empathy, and hope while addressing negative feelings like boredom and resentment can further support teachers' overall well-being and resilience. In planning psychosocial support services for teachers in the New Normal, it is essential to consider the potential benefits of stress management practices, positive psychology interventions, and mindfulness programs to address their unique needs and promote their overall well-being.

Methodology

Research Design

This qualitative study employs the phenomenological approach as the specific method in analyzing and describing the lived experiences of teachers on well-being in the new normal. The phenomenological methodology enables the researcher to elicit a rich and in-depth collection of narratives, stories, and a person's naturalistic first-hand experiences to illuminate ideas, generate knowledge, and make meaning out of the challenges, strategies, and opportunities they have experienced in their well-being (King, N., 2007). Since the study is concerned with meaning and how meaning was created from the experiences shared, the researcher will focus on description and relationship rather than causality and correlations of teachers' lived experiences (Giorgi A., Giorgi B., and Morley J., 2017).

Participants

Giorgi (2012) believes that it is not the sample size in this methodology that will help determine the effectiveness of the study, but the description of the phenomena is based on a person's experience. Purposive sampling was employed to determine qualified participants who met the following criteria:

- a. Full-time faculty member in the Basic Education department (across all levels) of the University.
- b. Teachers must have had a high level of stress in the past month before the opening of the new school year (during in-service training and preparations for full-face to face).
- c. Teachers with little to moderate well-being on any of the three major domains: Psychological, Physical Health, and Relationship.

Table 1 shows the profile of the participants who qualified from the criteria set in the study. It includes their sex, civil status, years of service, level or department and employment status.

Table 1. *The Demographic Profile of the Participants*

Teacher	Sex	Civil Status	Years of Service	Level/Department	Employment Status
1.1	Female	Single	3	Elementary	Probationary
1.2	Female	Married	2	Senior High School	Probationary
1.3	Female	Single	7	Senior High School	Probationary
1.4	Female	Single	3	Senior High School	Probationary
1.5	Female	Married	3	Elementary	Probationary
1.6	Female	Single	3	Senior High School	Probationary
1.7	Male	Single	6	Junior High School	Regular

Table 2 shows participants' high level of perceived stress as measured by PSS-10 tool, during the preparation and transition to face-to face learning.

Table 2. *Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) Results*

Teacher	Item Number										Raw Score	Description
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10		
T 1	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	4	3	3	30	HIGH
T 2	2	2	4	2	2	2	4	3	3	3	27	HIGH
T 3	3	2	3	2	3	3	4	4	3	2	29	HIGH
T 4	3	3	3	2	2	2	4	3	2	3	27	HIGH
T 5	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	28	HIGH
T 6	4	2	3	3	2	3	4	3	3	4	31	HIGH
T 7	3	3	3	3	2	4	3	2	2	2	27	HIGH

PSS Score Interpretation: Low Stress (0-14) ; Medium Stress (14-26) ; High Stress (26-40)

Table 3 shows the well-being profile of the teachers based on the three-sub scale of BBC Well-being Scale (Psychological, Physical and Relationship Scales). The results showed relationships as strength of teachers with level showing very much to extreme, while, psychological and physical health manifested little to moderate levels of wellbeing.

Table 3. BBC Well-being Scale Results

Teacher	Psychological			Physical Health			Relationship		
	RS	M	Description	R	M	Description	RS	M	Description
T1	35	2.9	A little	24	3.4	Moderately	19	3.8	Very Much
T2	38	3.2	Moderately	24	3.4	Moderately	24	4.8	Extremely
T3	28	2.3	A little	19	2.7	Moderately	21	4.2	Very Much
T4	29	2.4	A little	22	3.1	Moderately	22	4.4	Very Much
T5	36	3.0	Moderately	21	3.0	Moderately	23	4.6	Extremely
T6	29	2.4	A little	18	2.6	Moderately	20	4.0	Very Much
T7	27	2.3	A little	20	2.9	Moderately	22	4.4	Very Much

Instruments

The researcher primarily utilized in-depth interviews as a data-gathering tool to gain in-depth insights into teachers' well-being in the new normal. The questionnaire was formulated by researchers and validated by three (3) counselors. Data reliability depended on the openness of expressing their thoughts and feelings, questioning pre-understanding, and a reflective attitude in answering questions related to the eight (8) dimensions of their well-being (e.g. physical, intellectual, emotional, social, spiritual, vocational, financial, and environmental) within the context of the New Normal. This guided the researcher throughout the analysis and helped uphold consistency and validity (Sundler, Annelie & Lindberg, Elisabeth & Nilsson, Christina & Palmér, Lina.,2019).

Procedure

The study utilized purposive sampling, where participants were selected based on specific criteria determined by tools measuring stress and well-being levels. After obtaining the necessary approval for the study, teachers from a university in Pampanga were requested to complete the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) and BBC-Wellbeing Scale to identify participants meeting the criteria. Tables 1 to 3 provided participant inclusion details.

The researcher identified Seven (7) among those who qualified on the criteria, where they were informed of the research process. After this, they were scheduled for in-depth interviews to gather their stories and experiences, which served as the primary data for the study. Interviews were conducted either face-to-face or online, depending on participant availability and preference. With participants' consent, interviews were audio recorded and transcribed verbatim. The initial interview focused on building rapport, followed by subsequent interviews addressing specific dimensions of wellbeing. Follow-up sessions were scheduled as needed, ensuring data clarity and collection. Interviews were conducted 4-5 times, lasting approximately 30 minutes to 1 hour each.

Thematic analysis was utilized to examine the data, enabling researchers to delve into participants' experiences. Responses were transcribed and scrutinized to pinpoint recurring themes. The researcher fully immersed themselves in the collected data, meticulously reviewing transcripts to gain a profound understanding of teachers' experiences. This method, as outlined by Clark and Braun (2014), involved organizing patterns of meaning to condense similar responses into cohesive content.

Clark and Braun (2014) regarded this as an analytical method for analyzing and organizing patterns of meaning, allowing the researcher to streamline similar responses based on frequency into more robust and cohesive content. The study adhered to the six phases of thematic analysis proposed by Braun and Clarke (2014) beginning with familiarization of data, then coding, grouping of codes into themes, reviewing themes for coherence, defining and naming each theme, and finally writing up the analysis with data and literature context. To validate the reliability and meanings derived from the themes, the researcher conducted participant validation and sought expert validation from three Registered Guidance Counselors. The challenges identified served as the foundation for developing a proposed psychosocial support service for teachers.

Ethical Considerations

The study conducted among teachers followed ethical guidelines by ensuring informed consent, confidentiality, respect for participants, and beneficence. Participants were fully informed of the study's purpose and risks and benefits, their identities were protected, and their beliefs were respected. The researcher minimized potential harm and provided support resources if needed. Personal information was kept confidential and stored securely. The study was conducted without biases regarding participants' religious beliefs or personal principles. The researcher in this study considered beneficence by recognizing and minimizing potential risks to participants. They acknowledged that discussing sensitive topics related to well-being in the new normal could evoke distressing experiences and provided resources for support. Risks identified during in-depth interviews included personal habits, family issues, work-related stress, and emotional discomfort. The researcher made efforts to minimize these risks and offered emotional debriefing if needed. The debriefing process consisted of five stages focused on addressing traumatic experiences. Although participants may not directly benefit, their participation contributes to the expansion of knowledge and benefits psychosocial support services for teachers. The study also emphasized ethical approval and maintaining participant confidentiality when disseminating findings. Generally, the study prioritized ethical considerations and followed guidelines to ensure participant well-being through the conduct of the study.

Results and Discussion

The results and discussion of this study were derived from a thorough process of thematic analysis and presentation. The initial segment of the presentation focused on the personal experiences of university teachers in adapting to the new normal. It explored their individual perspectives on wellbeing, the unique challenges they faced, and the coping mechanisms they developed during this challenging period. The themes that emerged were based on the participants' reflective accounts and narratives, which were categorized according to various dimensions of wellbeing, including Vocational, Financial, Physical, Intellectual, Emotional, Social, Spiritual, and Environmental wellbeing. The development of these themes was visually represented in tables containing codes, subthemes and themes. The second part of the presentation shows the Proposed Psychosocial Support Services in response to the challenges identified and lastly, the implication of the study to Guidance and Counseling.

1. Lived Experiences of University Teachers on Wellbeing in the New Normal

1.1. Vocational Wellbeing

The table below showed positive perception of teachers amidst difficulties and challenges since the transition to full face to face learning in new normal education.

Table 4. *Personal View, Challenges and Coping Mechanisms Developed Supporting Vocational well-being*

Sample Verbatim	Verbatim	Sub-themes	Major themes
Personal View			
<p><i>"Ngayon, ayaw ko na maghanap ng other work aside from teaching. Ang hirap na lumabas sa comfort zone. I don't want to take a risk na walang kasiguraduhan na makakahanap (Now, I don't want to look for other work aside from teaching anymore. It's difficult to step out of my comfort zone. I don't want to take the risk of not being sure if I'll find a new work)" (T7)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Work considered a comfort zone -Passion and fulfillment in teaching -Experiencing the joy in teaching 	Teaching as a calling	
<p><i>"Mas ngayon ko narealize na teaching pala talaga ang gusto ko. After kong mag call center, I wanna go back to teaching kahit na compensation hindi maganda. Tiring sya pero gusto ko ang ginagawa ko (Now I realize that teaching is really what I want. After working in a call center, I want to go back to teaching even if the compensation isn't good. It's tiring but I love what I'm doing)" (T6)</i></p>			
<p>I teach for financial reasons, aside from that, my family needs money to survive, to have three meals a day and for emergencies to buy the things that we want."(T3)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Study benefits as motivation to teach 	Financial reward as Motivation	Positive View on Vocation
<p><i>Yung motivation, mga kids ko na, dahil din sa benefit, para sa educational benefits ng faculty dependent ko - mga kids ko..(My motivation is my kids, and also because of the benefits, to enjoy educational benefits of faculty dependent - my children.) (T5)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Working to provide for financial needs 		
<p>"for me, right now, I don't feel valued in terms of my skills and rate. In terms of appreciation, like thank you and the way of interactions, I am appreciated with my work. (T3)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Undervalued financially and skillfully but valued in other way 		
<p><i>Pag dating sa co-teachers/admin, narerecognize na good ako sa isang task. I feel valued kasi nacoconsider nila ako sa isang gawain at bagay na kaya ko at magaling ako (When it comes to co-teachers/administrators, they recognize that I am good at a certain task. I feel valued because they consider me capable and skilled in that area..) (T1)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Affirmation as motivation to work and validation of good works -Valuing one's capability and function in the group 	Recognition and appreciation	
Challenges			
<p><i>"Hindi match yung pagod mo, sa sahod na natatanggap mo, though sabi ko naman kumpara sa previous job ko, mas mataas naman dito, yun nga lang dito kahit tumaas sya, hindi padin, nacocompensate ang work. (The exhaustion doesn't match the salary you receive, although I did say that compared to my previous job, it's higher here. However,</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Lack of Financial satisfaction -Unmatched compensation to the amount of work 	Low salary	External Challenges Impacting Vocational Wellbeing

even though it's increased here, the work still isn't compensated)" (T1)

If I were given another chance and time, I would pursue another course; if given a chance today, I would go out of teaching, maybe because it's too stressful." (T1)

"Dahil nag wowork sa gabi, minsan papasok ka ng puyat, you're not in the right mood to deal with people. Since I have to deliver the work that's required, I have to sacrifice talaga yung sleep (Because I work at night, sometimes I come in feeling tired, not in the right mood to deal with people. Since I have to deliver the required work, I really have to sacrifice my sleep)"(T3)

"Sometimes, you're going to ask yourself,, what didn't I do right for them, why is their behavior like that and what became of our class, there are other students too who are incomplete, they also have personal problems, it really contributes to the stress" (T7)

dati pag may announcement or instructions iibigay lang. ngayon, pag may announcement, may tendency na mabago, kasi nung nag transition, parang trial and error. Hindi na ako sigurado ano dapat gawin ("Before, when there was an announcement or instructions, they would just be given. Now, when there's an announcement, there's a tendency for it to change because during the transition, it seemed like trial and error. I'm not sure anymore what should be done.)" (T2)

"Frustrations sa subject, na nahihirapan ang mga bata. Nafufrustate din ako. Dahil may mga bata hindi magandang foundations nila, nahihirapan sila. nafufrustate din ako, tinuro mo naman, parang kulang padin, ikaw ba ang ang kulang o talagang hirap lang ang bata. ("Frustrations with the subject, seeing the kids struggle. It's frustrating for me too. Because some kids don't have good foundations, they struggle. It's frustrating for me , even though I've taught them, it still feels lacking. Is it me who's lacking or are the kids really just struggling?)"(T2)

"Feeling ko nagkaroon ako ng separation anxiety with the family dahil nag face to face na and most of my time sa work. Nasanay kasi nung online nasa bahay lang ("I feel like I've developed separation anxiety from my family because we've transitioned to face-to-face interactions and most of my time is spent at work. I got used to being at home during the online setup)" T3

"Tinatapos ko na lahat sa school kahit mag stay ako, mag over time, basta matapos lang." (I finish everything at school even if I stay, do overtime, as long as I finish".) (T6)

"Pag nakakapagod na, Sleeping, yun yung pinaka me time ko. Gusto ko lang talaga mapag isa." (When I'm tired, Sleeping, that's my most me time. I just really want to be alone) (T7)

"Ngayong face- to- face, yung may nakakausap ka sa faculty, may teachers na makakarelate sa experience mo sa mga estudyante. Yung support system naging strong (Now that it's face-to-face, having someone to talk to among the faculty, having teachers who can relate to your experiences with the students. The support system has become strong.") (T2)

- Overwhelming workload
- Work-life imbalance
- Overworking and Sleep deprivation
- Comparison on the amount of stress in teaching from other professions
- time management struggles
- prolonged hours of work

Lack of boundaries work and personal life

- Challenging Students' behavior
- Adjustment to students' attention span

Student behavior issues

- uncertainty in tasks
- fear of failure to new tasks

Role ambiguity

- Frustrations to the results of teaching
- Doubting one's skill to teach
- Doubting the value of work

Doubts on self-efficacy

Internal Challenges Impacting Vocational Wellbeing

- Emotional adjustment at work
- Adjusting in work and personal routine
- flexible and adaptable to changes

Workplace and emotional adaptability

Coping Mechanism

- Accomplishing work at school
- Prioritizing immediate concern

Time management

- Keeping of sense of self or me time
- Optimism in the face of many concerns
- Setting boundary

Self-PreservatiOn

Problem-focused Coping

- Seeking Support from colleagues

Seeking Support from Colleagues

<i>"Hindi ko nalang muna iisipin ang problema, tuloy lang sa ginagawa (I don't think about the problem, I just keep doing it)" (T3 & T4)</i>	-Setting aside personal problems -Prioritizing concerns	Compartmentalization	Emotion-focused Coping
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THEME 1: Positive View on Vocation

University Teachers find the true essence of teaching as a vocation that is not only financially helpful but also comes with deep appreciation and value. During the transition to onsite learning in the new normal, teachers still acknowledged teaching as their comfort zone and a career they were called for, amidst challenges. Being acknowledged and respected for their dedication, heightened their sense of fulfillment and appreciation to their work, creating a positive cycle of motivation and dedication. The financial rewards, though not considered high, helps them provide for their personal and family needs. This motivates them to stay in the profession.

Sub-theme 1.1 Teaching as Calling

Teaching in the new normal helped teachers discover their purpose and meaning through self-reflection. Psychology defines the comfort zone as a state where a person operates in a familiar way without taking risks. Despite challenges in teacher retention, some teachers find comfort in teaching due to their alignment with the job and desire for career growth. Comfortable teachers are more likely to engage in professional development and implement innovative teaching practices. According to Ingersoll & Strong, (2011), when teachers are satisfied and comfortable with their jobs, they are more likely to persist in their role.

This is evident on all participants' reflection, comparing their previous job to teaching experience saying that, "Mas ngayon ko narealize na teaching pala talaga ang gusto ko. After kong mag call center, I wanna go back to teaching kahit na compensation hindi maganda. Tiring sya pero gusto ko ang ginagawa ko. (IDI-CT 6), "Now I realize that teaching is really what I want. After working in a call center, I want to go back to teaching even if the compensation isn't good. It's tiring but I love what I'm doing. (IDI-CT 6)". with the desire to teach comes they experienced as expressed by teacher 2, saying "Sa ngayon sir, okay naman nag eenjoy naman ako sa work and gusto ko din kasi talaga magturo, I feel fulfilled, "For now sir, I'm okay, I'm enjoying the work and I really want to teach, I feel fulfilled. (IDI-CT2).

Sub-theme 1.2: Financially Rewarding

Teachers during the new normal continue teaching primarily for financial reasons, to provide for their personal and family needs. Job satisfaction is often lower in private schools compared to public schools due to wage gaps. Teachers cite providing for their families as their main motivation for teaching, saying that, Financial reasons aside from that, my family needs money to survive, to have three meals a day and for emergencies to buy the things that we want. (IDI-T3). Perhaps my motivation is to provide money for my family, for financial reasons alone. (IDI-T7)" Aside from the compensation, teachers with children look forward to the benefits of faculty dependents saying that, "The motivation, my kids, because of the benefits too, to make my kids dependent on the faculty. (IDI- T5)

Research shows that proper incentives and promotion opportunities are key to retaining teachers in the profession (Msuya, O. W., 2016). It supported the data presented by UNESCO (2021) pointed out personal motivations as the main reason teachers enter and remain in the profession in which remuneration plays a major role.

Sub-theme 1.3: Recognition and appreciation

For employees and most importantly for teachers, recognizing, valuing, and appreciating their work is essential in their overall vocational well-being. Teacher 3 said that "...I don't feel valued in terms of my skills and rate. In terms of appreciation, like thank you and the way of interactions, I am appreciated with my work (IDI-CT 3)", which means that despite of lack in financial fulfillment in teaching, teachers are motivated to pursue teaching by the appreciation, like simple gestures of gratitude and friendly interactions, that for them, signifies sense of valuing at work.

In relation to this, the affirmation is also reflected on how admin provide positive and constructive feedback as shared by teacher 1, saying that, "sa admin, yung pagbibigay saamin ng feedback pag ang oobserve sila, maggandang comments and mataas na rating, natutuwa ako at namomotivate. Pagdating sa value ko, mas nakakapag bigay ng value ko dito ay mga bata, dahil sa evaluations makikita mo talaga. "When it comes to the admin, the feedback they give us when they observe us, with good comments and high ratings, makes me happy and motivated. When it comes to my value, the ones who really give value to me here are the children because in evaluations, you can really see it. (IDI-T1)" apart from the comments of the admin or coordinators, teachers appreciate her value through the positive feedback of the students that encouraged her to give more. Another expression of valuing experienced by the teacher when their work are acknowledged and considered to perform a certain function, saying that, "Just the privilege alone (of being given a position in 2 years of stay), when I thought about it, I already felt valued. (IDI-T2)" empowering teachers to assume important tasks significantly impart value on teachers. This is also agreed by teacher 1, adding the recognition in doing the task well adds up to their value which also means, being endowed with trust on a person gives a significant sense of value that makes them feel good and validates one's importance in the workplace. Teacher 5 expressed this saying that, "Nafefel ko naman ang importance ko, na kapag wala ako, may kulang sa function.I feel like nasa work ang worth ko." "I feel my importance, that when I'm not around, something is missing in the function. I feel like my worth is in my work. (IDI-CT5)". During the COVID-19 pandemic, teachers faced unprecedented challenges,

including transitioning to online learning and managing hybrid classrooms. With appreciation and support from colleagues, administrators, and the community, teachers were able to thrive as expressed in their response. This experience of empowerment is a crucial aspect of teachers' work attitude, fostering job satisfaction, and involvement, increasing productivity and engagement, and demonstrating their commitment during the pandemic. Teachers who feel appreciated are better equipped to provide quality education and emotional support to their students. This fosters a positive work environment, benefiting teachers and the entire school community (Bascia, N., 2022).

THEME 2: External Challenges Impacting Vocational Wellbeing

In the realm of vocational well-being, teachers face a myriad of external challenges that significantly impact their overall satisfaction and sense of fulfillment in their profession. Based on their narratives, Low salary, lack of boundaries between work and personal life, Student behavior issues and role ambiguity were seen as concerns on their overall vocational wellbeing. Financial strain was experienced by educators due to inadequate compensation for their valuable contributions. This leads to feelings of undervaluation and financial instability, ultimately affecting their job satisfaction. Additionally, the blurred lines between work and personal life exacerbate vocational challenges as teachers struggle to maintain a healthy balance, resulting in increased stress, burnout, and reduced overall well-being. On the other hand, the changes brought by different modalities affect the development of student behavior issues, such as disruptions and disciplinary problems, which add further stress and strain on teachers. It leads to further concern of role ambiguity, where teachers may feel uncertain about their responsibilities and expectations, because the uncertainty of COVID situation complicates their vocational well-being by fostering feelings of frustration and inadequacy. By addressing these issues, we can enhance teachers' vocational satisfaction and overall well-being, ultimately creating a more positive and supportive environment for educators.

Sub-themes 2.1. Low salary and Lack of boundaries work and personal life

Most teacher respondents feel they are not paid enough for the hard work they do, leading to low morale and retention issues. This is common especially to majority of teachers who are in probationary status like teacher 3 saying that, "Actually, I'm a probationary faculty even though I've been working for 7 years already, my salary isn't that high, especially with expenses nowadays, it's not the salary that you can live off of." Similarly, teacher 1 compared the amount they get from the workload saying that, "The exhaustion you feel doesn't match the salary you receive, though I did say that compared to my previous job, it's higher here. However, even though it has increased here, the work still isn't compensated enough." . This wage disparity can lead to significant teacher shortages and have an impact on teacher morale and retention of teachers in the country (Tarraya, 2023). However, some teachers like Teacher 2 find fulfillment in their work through personal and professional growth, productivity, and work-life balance saying that, "Its is really up to you on how you will see your work, it will not be enough if you will bring home all your work, but if you are productive at school and efficient, it is enough, personally it is okay since you are meeting the children, interacting with them, co teacher and there is growth". Overall, teacher salaries and working conditions greatly impact job satisfaction and retention, ultimately affecting educational quality.

While salary is one of the primary concerns, it becomes heavier due to feelings of regret and dissatisfaction in teaching coming from the amount of stress they experience. The phenomenon showed the reality of teaching job as susceptible to high burnout rates and occupational stress over the last decade (Kyriacou, 2015) which had increased especially during the surge of the pandemic. This stress manifests in how they view their vocation and the purpose of pursuing it. One of them said that "Naisip ko din na mag bussiness nalang instead na magturo, kasi nakakastress talaga ang pagtuturo" (I thought of putting up a bussiness instead of continuing teaching). Another participant expressed her regret in teaching as it was too stressful, saying " If I am given another chance and time, I will pursue another course; if given a chance today, I will go out of teaching, maybe because it's too stressful". Garcia-Álvarez et al. (2021) shared the same finding, saying that the return to face-to-face instruction caused teachers to experience high levels of stress, anxiety, and even depression. These emotions were probably made worse by their emotional experience during the lockdown, the uncertainty surrounding the spread of the illness in schools and managing their workload from home.

Sub-themes 2.2 Student behavior issues and Role ambiguity

Teachers experience classroom management deficits, which means difficulty sustaining order, discipline, and an optimal learning atmosphere in their classrooms. This can be an important barrier to effective teaching and causes teachers' stress and negative motivations. Student change in behavior is one of the primary concerns of the teachers:

Simula nung last school year dahil bagong kawala sila, grabe yung behavior nila as in. Most of your stress as teacher, nanggagaling don, Yung mga concerns ng advisory class ko lang talaga ang problema. ("Since last school year, because they're newly released, their behavior has been really extreme. Most of your stress as a teacher comes from there, only the concerns of my advisory class are really the problem." IDI-CT4).

Stress sa mga bata, dahil siguro iba ang ugali nila ngayon, ang hirap nilang ihandle. Syempre, pagiging disrespectful nila, merong ganoon. Meron ding ganon' dito.. "There's stress with the kids, maybe because their attitudes are different now, they're difficult to handle. Of course, their disrespectfulness, there's that. There's also that here.", IDI-CT1)

The following affirmed signs of COVID-19 experience that has significantly influenced both teacher stress and student behavior even up to this time. The online distance learning enabled the students to have felt unfavorably, aggressively, changed their social routines,

and struggled with mental health conditions like anxiety, depression, and insomnia (İlhan, Çiçek., Ahmet, Tanhan., Selami, Tanriverdi., 2020)

In addition, despite teaching for years, teachers acknowledge the difficulty in handling concerns in this time. Also, adjusting to a new position or line of work has been a challenge for one of the teachers saying that, Maraming uncertainties akala ko alam ko na nangangapa padin lalo na sa bagong posisyon IDI-CT2. For her, teaching is somewhat manageable however, administrative jobs remain to be a source of stress for her especially during face-to-face. There is also a sense of adjustment and uncertainty in roles given which suggests the need for training and hands-on mentoring to improve teachers' effectiveness and uphold their role confidently.

THEME 3: Internal Challenges impacting Vocational Wellbeing

Doubts on self-efficacy and Workplace and emotional adaptability were two internal challenges encountered by the teachers. Following a significant disruption in education like the COVID-19 pandemic, teachers, particularly Teachers 7 and 5, express self-doubt and frustration regarding poor student performance during online classes. They tend to attribute failures to themselves and credit success to students, reflecting a lack of satisfaction and self-efficacy in teaching saying that:

"Sometimes, you're going to ask yourself e, anong mali ko, anong hindi ko nagawang tama sa kanila, bakit ganon ang behavior nila at naging outcome ng klase namin, may mga other students pa na incomplete, may mga personal problems din, nakakacontribute talaga sa stress. ("Sometimes, you're going to ask yourself what did I do wrong, what didn't I do right for them, why is their behavior like that and what became of our class, there are other students who are incomplete, there are personal problems too, it really contributes to the stress, IDI- T7)

I feel like i'm not enough as a teacher and as a parent, parang may gusto akong patunayan, feeling ko yun din ang view ng tao for me. (I feel like I'm not enough as a teacher and as a parent, it's like I want to prove something, I feel like that's also how people view me.. IDI-T5)."

Teacher 5 acknowledges the impact of online learning on student performance but feels inadequate as both a teacher and a parent, driven by a desire to prove themselves to others. These sentiments underscore the significant emotional toll and sense of responsibility teachers experience amidst the challenges of remote education.

Additionally, the transition from online to face-to-face teaching has challenged teachers to adapt their routines, with some struggling to readjust to the demands of in-person instruction. Teacher 7 expresses difficulty in managing time and personal rest between classes, contrasting the flexibility of online teaching. However, for Teachers 6 and 2, Minsan meron kami yung mga abrupt changes, biglaang meeting and biglang changes in schedule., "kasi dati pag may announcement iibigay lang. ngayon, pag may announcement, may tendency na mabago, kasi nung nag transition, parang trial and error. . They appreciate the development of flexibility and adaptability to abrupt changes in the onsite setup, though acknowledging the need for trial and error in the transition process. This shift has also affected personal time with family, leading to emotional adjustments and separation anxiety, as noted by Teacher 3 saying, "Feeling ko nagkaroon ako ng Separation anxeity with the family dahil nag face to face na and most of my time sa work. Nasanay kasi nung online nasa bahay lang". Despite challenges, teachers generally prefer face-to-face instruction for its potential to streamline procedures and improve outcomes.

THEME 4: Problem-focused Coping (Time management, Self-Preservation and Seeking Support from Colleagues)

Teachers developed more problem-focused coping strategies such as Time management, Self-Preservation and Seeking Support from Colleagues to navigate multifaceted challenges for teachers during this transition to full face to face learning. As teachers navigate this shift, they grapple with the need to readjust their time management strategies to accommodate in-person classroom demands, striking a balance between professional responsibilities and personal well-being. This has been found essential in coping with workload concern and imbalance between personal and professional life. Strategies like completing tasks at school, utilizing overtime, and prioritizing assignments enable them to allocate time effectively, as exemplified by Teacher 5 saying that, "I tried to do everything at school so I wouldn't bring work home, I tried to do everything at school so I wouldn't bring work home". This shift towards managing tasks within designated hours reflects a desire to maintain a work-life balance. Moreover, for teacher 4, scheduling and prioritizing tasks were also found to be effective in handling the demands of their profession saying that "I label him as high prio, mid prio or low prio. If it's a high prio, and he's really needed tomorrow, I really reply. But if it can wait until tomorrow, I mean I will read it."

Additionally, the return to face-to-face instruction requires teachers to prioritize self-preservation, ensuring they maintain physical and emotional health amidst the heightened demands of in-person teaching. Teacher 2 for example is prioritizing sleep as "me time". Teacher 3 highlights the challenge of achieving rest and advocates for practices like listening to music and short periods of self-isolation as forms of coping saying that, you can't really get the literal rest and spend a peaceful moment, listening to music, not talking to people for a while. Additionally, setting boundaries is also a form of self-preservation according to teacher 3, saying that they are not allowed to talk to me at lunch time, giving boundaries with the students in terms of time. While, maintaining optimism in facing daily challenges, are expressed by Teachers 4 and 5, noting how crucial it is in the profession. This is aligned with the research of Song K. (2022), which emphasizes the importance of nurturing optimism among teachers for enhancing job resources and overall well-being, ultimately facilitating career direction and dynamic coping strategies.

Lastly, seeking support from colleagues becomes paramount during this transition, as educators lean on their peers for guidance, collaboration, and solidarity in navigating the complexities of returning to the physical classroom environment. Overall, the transition to face-to-face learning underscores the resilience and adaptability of teachers, as they strive to meet the evolving needs of their students while preserving their own vocational well-being.

THEME 5: Emotion-focused Coping (Compartmentalization)

Another coping mechanism applied by teachers is avoidance. Teachers were found to ignore other problems and confront the present concern. For instance, teacher 3 and 4 both said that, “Hindi ko nalang muna iisipin ang problema, tuloy lang sa ginagawa (I don't think about the problem, I just keep doing it)” likewise, teacher 5 said that, “Hindi ako msyadong nag dedwell sa problem ko sa work e feeling ko napeperform ko naman ng maayos ang pagtuturo kahit may personal problem, hindi ko din naman sa kinla pwede ishare yun. (I don't dwell too much on my problems at work and I feel that I can perform well in teaching even though I have personal problems, I can't share that with them either.)” This affirmed the study of Minz, N.S, (2023) claiming that Teachers with the least and most professional work experience frequently employ avoidance and manipulation as non-adaptive coping mechanisms. Additionally, Teachers also manifested the same findings of that despite personal stress and anxiety, they tend to consciously adopt a positive outlook and engage in activities to restore their well-being. In the case of the teachers, addressing present concern and setting aside other concerns showed flexibility and capacity to manage problems, however, avoiding thinking and confronting other problems became their negative form of coping (Beltman, S., Hascher T., Mansfield F., 2022).

1.2. Financial well-being

Table below showed negative perceptions of teachers on financial well-being, amidst internal struggles experienced and challenges since the transition to full face to face learning in new normal education.

Table 5. Personal View, Challenges and Coping Mechanisms developed supporting Financial well-being.

Sample Verbatim	Codes	Sub-themes	Major themes
Personal View			
<p>“Pwede na, enough naman siguro, marami lang siguro akong personal expenses... more on wants. Self-satisfaction sya for me na mabibili ko din ang gusto ko (“It's probably enough for now [salary], but I might have a lot of personal expenses... more on wants. It's a sense of self-satisfaction for me that I can eventually buy what I want.”) (T5)</p>	<p>Enjoying salary through Self-indulgence Prioritizing wants for Self-satisfaction.</p>	<p>Indulgent self-satisfaction</p>	
<p>“I feel the stress in budgeting, pag payday pero, kinakaya naman (“I feel the stress of budgeting, especially on payday, but I manage to cope with it.”) (T3)</p>	<p>Stress in budgeting</p>	<p>Financial Pressure/Anxiety</p>	<p>Negative view on Financial wellbeing</p>
<p>“Nadidismaya ako at nalulungkot pag hindi ako nakapag bigay sa bahay sa dami ng gastusin ngayon (“I feel disappointed and saddened when I can't contribute to the household with the amount of expenses we have now.”) (T4)</p>	<p>Disappointment with financial limitation</p>		
Challenges			
<p>Nung nag face-to-face, nandon na madaming naging expenses. Wala na akong maibudget. Financially, yun talaga ang struggle ko. Since ngayon I am living paycheck to pay check, hindi ako nakakapag ipon, kasi ive been teaching for 3 years pero wala kong ipon. (“When we transitioned face-to-face, there were a lot of expenses involved. I couldn't budget anymore. Financially, that's really my struggle. Since now I am living paycheck to paycheck, I can't save because even though I've been teaching for 3 years, I don't have any savings.”) (T6)</p>	<p>The financial difficulty caused by new expenses Financial difficulty by Availing credits/loans to survive Transportation cost, and work distance</p>	<p>Lack of Financial Readiness</p>	
<p>“Gusto kong mag ipon, mahirap lang kasi halos walang natitira.” (“I want to save, but it's difficult because there's almost nothing left.”) (T6)</p>			<p>Internal struggle on Finances</p>
<p>“Hindi na masyado nakakaipon, most of my salary, pambayad ng apartment, sa bahay, kung ano matira, yun na yung saakin. Sa savings hindi ako masyado nakakasave. Pinakasaving ko na siguro doon ay yung sa cooperative. (“I'm not able to save much anymore. Most of my salary goes towards paying for the apartment, household expenses, whatever is left is for me. I'm not able to save much. Probably the most</p>	<p>Immediate expenses after quarantine periods Credits and loan concern</p>	<p>Struggles on Saving</p>	

I've saved is in the cooperative.") (T7)

Coping Mechanisms

Kapag weekends, tumutulong sa family business para macover ang ibang expenses (on weekends, helping the family business to cover other expenses) (T2)

Meron naman akong side jobs, sa insurance company, kahit papaano nakakatulong naman sa gastusin (I have side jobs, at the insurance company, somehow it helps with our expenses). (T5)

"Kahit may loans, nag sasave kami sa MP2 Pag-ibig savings and cooperatives. Hindi ko din kasi kaya na ako ang mag keep ng pera by myself." (Even with loans, we save on MP2 Pag-ibig savings and cooperatives. I can't even keep the money by myself"). (T5)

Finding Alternative financial sources

Adjusting location to work to lessen costs

Looking for ways to save or invest money in business

Alternative financial sources

Efforts of saving

Problem-Focused Financial coping

THEME 6: Negative view on Financial wellbeing

The COVID 19 pandemic has brought economic challenges to people especially to teachers. Financial wellbeing refers to being able to meet present and future financial needs, feeling secure about finances, and having the freedom to make choices that enhance quality of life. Teachers view their wellbeing negatively highlighting financial attitudes such as indulgent self-satisfaction and financial pressure/anxiety.

Subtheme 6.1 Indulgent Self Satisfaction

Teachers' motivation in spending plays a vital role in their financial well-being. One teacher mentioned that her salary is sufficient to cover her expenses, with most of it going toward fulfilling her wants. Another teacher expressed that her motivation to spend is for leisure and enjoyment, supported by her husband who encourages her to go out and buy things she desires. This shift in spending behavior can be attributed to a change in roles, as the teacher transitioned from being the primary provider to focusing on personal enjoyment after marriage. Young professionals often find joy in spending on items they desire, seeing it as a source of self-satisfaction. Emotional factors and beliefs have a significant impact on financial decisions, influencing risk-taking behaviors based on the type of emotions experienced. While personal spending can bring happiness, research suggests that spending on others or engaging in prosocial activities can result in even greater satisfaction. Sharing expenses with others can further enhance the joy derived from spending money (Aknin, L. B., Dunn, E. W., Proulx, J., Lok, I., & Norton, M. I., 2020).

Subtheme 6.2. Financial Pressures and Anxiety

Teachers' financial challenges have become more pronounced since the shift to full face-to-face teaching, impacting them emotionally. In line with a study on financial well-being, teachers have shown signs of financial anxiety, characterized by persistent worry and unease regarding financial responsibilities. Teachers 3 and 5 elaborated on this, with Teacher 3 expressing, "I feel the stress of budgeting, especially on payday, but I manage to handle it.," and Teacher 5 adding, "I'm very stressed about finances because of the numerous expenses, especially when I stay up late caring for my baby." These educators cited difficulties with budgeting, particularly around payday, as a major source of their stress, leading to worry during these times. Beyond financial anxiety, teachers also grapple with various stressors that compound their overall stress levels. The profession of teaching, known for its relatively low income, presents economic stress for educators. Research led by Stanford in the USA in 2020 pointed out that younger teachers are more likely to experience economic anxiety due to lower salaries, the absence of dual-income households, and high housing costs. Economically anxious teachers tend to harbor negative feelings about their jobs, exhibit poor attendance, and have a 50% higher likelihood of leaving their school district within two years. This economic stress is similarly reflected in the Philippines, where teachers face challenges such as inadequate pay and large class sizes, contributing to the perceived stress and dissatisfaction in their work. For young professionals like Teachers 4 and 6, the pressure to provide for their families adds to their financial concerns, intensifying their stress and job dissatisfaction. They expressed feelings of disappointment and sadness concerning their inability to meet their family's needs, as highlighted by Teacher 4 saying, "I feel disappointed and sad when I can't contribute at home," and Teacher 6 sharing, "It saddens me that I can't help at home because of this. Luckily, my mother is abroad, so she assists me." Clearly, financial anxiety among teachers leads to fixation on financial matters and feelings of inadequacy due to restrictive incomes. The lack of financial resources intensifies their stress, potentially leading to emotional distress and, in severe cases, depression. Prolonged exposure to financial stress and the challenges of managing fluctuating income may further jeopardize teachers' mental well-being. Therefore, in addition to advocating for salary increases, initiatives like financial education and literacy can empower teachers to navigate these financial pressures effectively (Guan et al., 2022)

THEME 7: Internal struggle on Finances

The internal struggles teachers face regarding financial readiness and saving can be closely tied to the context of the new normal and the transition to face-to-face teaching. With the shift to new teaching modalities, teachers may have had to adapt their financial habits and preparations to accommodate changes in their work environment. The uncertainty and adjustments brought about by transitioning back to face-to-face teaching could have impacted their ability to effectively manage new forms expenses, leading to these struggles in financial readiness and saving.

Subtheme 7.1 Lack of Financial Readiness

The shift in work setup due to the decreased case of COVID-19 has significantly impacted teachers' financial well-being as they transitioned from remote or hybrid learning back to full face-to-face teaching. This change brought about emerging expenses that have challenged teachers' financial readiness, leading to struggles with budgeting and saving. Teachers articulated difficulties in managing expenses related to groceries, utilities, inflation, and additional responsibilities, expressing that their finances were stretched thin. The adjustment to face-to-face teaching necessitated allocating funds for transportation and accommodation near the school, leading to financial strain for many teachers. Some resorted to borrowing money or relying on loans to cover their expenses, contributing to a cycle of debt and limited savings. Enhancing financial literacy, especially in record-keeping and financial planning, could help teachers make more informed decisions and curb impulsive spending, ultimately improving their financial well-being in the face of these challenges.

Subtheme 7.2 Struggles on Saving

Amidst job security concerns during the pandemic, the transition to face to face work significantly impacted teachers' financial responsibilities by increasing expenses related to transportation, office attire, and meals. This change potentially led to increased disposable income for teachers. Interviews revealed teachers expressing a desire to save despite the financial demands of returning to full onsite work. One teacher indicated challenges in saving due to various expenses, especially prioritizing personal and family needs over savings. Managing finances and unexpected costs posed difficulties for some teachers, while cooperative programs offered alternative saving options. Teachers emphasized the importance of balancing expenses and savings, with some relying on support from spouses or cooperative programs to manage finances effectively. The study of Nalasa-Costuna and Tantiado (2023) emphasized the significance of financial literacy, investments, and savings for teachers' financial well-being, highlighting the need for tailored financial planning and education to enhance teachers' financial capabilities in managing their finances and fostering a better understanding of budgeting within the context of family dynamics and dual-income households.

THEME 8. Problem-Focused Financial coping (adjusting budget and efforts in saving)

The financial struggles faced by teachers amidst the transition to face-to-face teaching are multifaceted, encompassing issues such as adjusting to increased expenses due to the shift in teaching modalities and the need to budget effectively to cope with financial challenges. Teachers have resorted to problem-focused coping mechanisms such as saving and adjusting budget by seeking accommodations closer to school to reduce commuting costs, taking on part-time jobs or engaging in side businesses to supplement their income, and emphasizing the importance of saving through schemes like MP2 and cooperatives. Additionally, the pressure to balance a limited salary with family responsibilities has led teachers to explore alternative financial sources and focus on efforts to save for future financial security despite obstacles like easy access to credit and lack of savings discipline. Recognizing the importance of financial literacy and seeking guidance in budgeting and saving strategies are essential steps for teachers to navigate these financial hurdles and ensure their long-term financial well-being, especially as they account for factors such as age and changing family dynamics in their financial planning.

1.3 Emotional well-being

Table below showed mostly positive perceptions of teachers on emotional well-being, amidst internal emotional challenges experienced since the transition to full face to face learning in new normal education. Emotional coping strategies were employed.

Table 6. *Personal View, Challenges and Coping Mechanisms developed supporting Emotional well-being.*

<i>Sample Verbatim</i>	<i>Codes</i>	<i>Sub-themes</i>
Personal View		
<i>“Masaya ako, lalo na pag nasa school at nakikita mga bata, mas nagiging happy ako.” (I’m happy, especially when I’m at school and seeing children, I’m happier)”. (T3)</i>	-Finding fulfillment and happiness in life	Striving to maintain happiness
<i>“Masaya ako kasi alam ko nandyan ang family ko para saakin thankful ako sa kanila, kahit medyo malayo kami sa isat isa.” (I’m happy because I know my family is there for me, I’m thankful for them, even though we’re a little far from each other)”(T6)</i>	-Trying to be motivated and happy	

<p><i>"Aware naman ako sa nararamdaman ko, yun nga siguro ang strength ko, sensitive ako."</i> (I'm aware of my feelings, maybe that's my strength, I'm sensitive). (T3)</p>	Understanding emotion rationalizing feelings	Emotional Awareness as Strength
<p><i>"Yun siguro ang natutunan ko sa pandemic, kung paano ako maging aware sa nararamdaman ko, pag stress, malungkot, masaya, natutunan kong basahin sarili kong emosyon."</i> (Maybe that's what I learned from the pandemic, how to be aware of my feelings, when stressed, sad, happy, I learned to read my own emotions). (T4)</p>		
Challenges		
<p><i>"I feel like something is lacking, hinahanap ko pa din yung happiness talaga."</i>(I feel like something is lacking, I'm still searching for true happiness.) (T5)</p>	-Not being contented and fulfilled in professional and personal life.	Lack of Happiness/ Fulfillment
<p><i>"Nafustrate ako pag hindi siya nag work according sa gusto ko, hirap ako minsan maka get over sa feeling na yun, siguro it will take some days pa."</i> (I get frustrated when he doesn't work according to what I want, sometimes it's hard for me to get over that feeling, maybe it will take some more days.) (T6)</p>	-Self-blaming oneself and feeling frustrated to work related stress	Frustrations leading to Self-doubts
<p><i>"Ngayon busy na outside our home, I feel not sharing to my husband, kasi minsan parang sya mismo hindi na sya interesado to listen sa mga problems ko, Kaya sinasarili ko nalang, kaya ko naman. But im trying to understand naman."</i> (Now that we are busy outside home, I feel not sharing it with my husband, because sometimes it seems like he himself is no longer interested in listening to my problems, so I just keep it to myself, I can do it. But i'm trying to understand). (T4)</p>	-Not considering feelings and emotions -Lack of emotional support from friends and family	Emotional Neglect
<p><i>"Pag nag pipile up na ang work at hindi nakakapag pass ontime, grabe naanxious talaga ako when work piles up and I can't pass on time, I get really anxious."</i> (T1)</p>	-Fear and uncertainty -Stress at work causing worriedness	Anxiety
<p><i>"Anxious ako sa problems na hindi namin masolusyunan agad agd kagaya ng pera, pag di nakakapag bigay sa family."</i> (I'm anxious about the problem that we can't solve right away, like money, if we can't give it to the family). (T3)</p>		
Coping Mechanisms		
<p><i>"Nung napag aralan ko na, na kaya kong maging masaya kahit ako lang mag isa. Kailangan mag desisyon ako on my own, ways, kumakalma muna ako tinitignan ko ang possible sides, I will have my own decision, magtatanong ako to validate at tama ang naiisip ko. ("After I learned that I can be happy even if I'm alone, I realized that I need to make decisions on my own. I take my time to calm down and consider the possible sides, then I come up with my own decision. I ask questions to validate if what I'm thinking is correct.")</i> (T6, similar to T7 & 3)</p>	-Managing emotions through expression to trusted friends -Sharing feelings and emotional state	Emotional Regulation
<p><i>"Food talaga ang way ko para maovercome ko yung stress."</i> (Food is really my way to overcome stress)- (T2 & T3)</p>	Food to feel good in confronting stress Food as means of relaxation and cool down from stress	Stress Eating
<p><i>"Medyo magastos talaga ako, kasi yun yung way ko to destress."</i> (I'm quite expensive, because that's my way to destress) (T5)</p>		
<p><i>"Iiyak talaga, pag nailabas ko na okay na ako."</i> (I'm really going to cry, when I let it out; I'm okay)- (T1)</p>	Crying as a way to express and lessen emotional concerns	Catharsis
<p><i>"Crying, sometimes even crying, because it makes me feel better."</i> (Umiiyak, minsan hagulgol pa, nakakagaan kasi ng pakiramdam I) (T4)</p>		

THEME 9: Positive view on Emotions

Fostering teachers' happiness is paramount for their effectiveness both at home and in the classroom. For instance, Teacher 1's acknowledgment of feeling "good and happy now but not super good just right... I can handle it" reflects resilience amid challenging work situations. Celebrating small victories and finding joy amidst overwhelming tasks demonstrate a positive outlook and coping mechanism. Teachers like Teacher 4.1 and 6 find happiness in their relationships, indicating the importance of feeling loved and supported, whether it's from family members, partners, or colleagues. This support system not only lessens the impact of problems but also boosts resilience. Moreover, creating a supportive school environment further enhances teachers' happiness, as seen in Teacher 3's

statement about feeling happier when engaging with students at school.

Investing in teachers' well-being and emotional intelligence is crucial for creating a conducive learning atmosphere and fostering better educational outcomes. The correlation between teachers' happiness, job satisfaction, and emotional intelligence, as highlighted in the study by Fernández et al. (2021), underlines the importance of these factors in promoting positive work attitudes and reducing turnover intention. Developing emotional awareness, as Teacher 3 acknowledges as their strength, helps teachers manage negative emotions and nurture positive ones, ultimately enhancing personal well-being and the learning environment. As demonstrated by teachers' experiences during the pandemic, recognizing and processing emotions, asking for help when needed, and being aware of emotional stability are essential skills that enable teachers to navigate challenges effectively. This emotional awareness not only benefits teachers in managing their own feelings but also allows them to better support students who may be encountering difficulties. In essence, emotional awareness is a valuable asset for teachers, enabling them to cultivate strong relationships, understand individual needs, and create a positive educational setting beneficial to all stakeholders.

THEME 10: Internal Emotional Challenges

Prioritizing authentic happiness among teachers is essential for their well-being, impacting their roles within families and schools. Teachers' positive emotions play a crucial role in shaping positive work attitudes, according to Lomas T. & VanderWeele TW. (2021). However, the pursuit of happiness can sometimes arise from feelings of unfulfillment and discontent, lacking a sense of purpose, connection, or inner peace. Teachers, such as those highlighted in the study ("I feel like something is lacking, hinahanap ko pa din yung happiness talaga," "Masaya pero I feel like I have to do something more para mas maging masaya pa," "Hindi ko masabi, masaya naman pero hindi ganon kasaya.. Kulang pa"), express the quest for true happiness amidst challenges. This pursuit reflects their persistence and openness to exploring avenues for finding completeness, highlighting the importance of continuous search, risk-taking, stepping out of comfort zones, and embracing new experiences, which are evident themes in teachers' professional lives. Supporting teachers' happiness is crucial, as it directly influences their job engagement and enthusiasm. Efforts to enhance workplace well-being necessitate the inclusion of emotional skills in teacher preparation programs to facilitate holistic support and encourage emotional well-being among educators.

Emotional challenges such as anxiety, self-doubt, frustration, and emotional neglect can significantly impact teachers' mental and emotional well-being. Teachers experience varying levels of stress and anxiety related to work demands, deadlines, family concerns, and financial pressures. These feelings are exacerbated when there is a lack of support and validation from loved ones, leading to emotional neglect and increased distress. Teachers who struggle with self-concept and self-efficacy may feel inadequate in their roles, contributing to feelings of doubt and insecurity. Moreover, anxiety stemming from job-related stressors, family issues, and financial constraints can overwhelm teachers, affecting their overall mental health. Encouraging emotional resilience, self-compassion, and effective stress management strategies is crucial to help teachers navigate these challenges and promote a healthier work environment. By addressing these emotional complexities and building supportive frameworks, institutions can better equip teachers to cope with the multifaceted demands of their profession while prioritizing their well-being and mental health.

THEME 11: Emotional Coping

During the transition to face-to-face experiences in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic, emotional coping strategies were considered a common tool for teachers in managing feelings of uncertainty, and stress. Specifically, teachers utilize emotion regulation strategies involving support seeking. They also utilize stress eating to overcome stress and Catharsis to release negative emotions.

Subtheme 11.1. Emotion Regulation through seeking support

In her study on Filipino teachers facing stress, Mingoa (2017) found that heavy workloads, resource scarcity, and poor relationships are common concerns in the workplace. Teachers utilize direct action and palliative techniques such as problem-solving and seeking social support to manage these stresses. It is evident that teachers recognize the importance of seeking social support to express emotions. For example, Teacher 4 acknowledges the value of confiding in close friends and her boyfriend during difficult times, highlighting a reluctance to share with family members. Married teachers like Teacher 2 also find solace in opening up to their spouses and siblings, emphasizing how the level of connection and relationship dynamics influence their willingness to share. Additionally, Teacher 1 emphasizes choosing trusted colleagues and non-judgmental individuals like her boyfriend to express her emotions openly.

However, some teachers, particularly those who are married, express hesitation in sharing their problems with their spouses or family members due to fears of unsupportive responses or lack of understanding. This reluctance to seek help is also observed in Teachers 6 and 7, who prefer relying on their own decision-making capabilities and avoiding vulnerability by not sharing their problems with others.

Overall, teachers emphasize the importance of expressing their emotions and seeking support to alleviate the psychological and emotional burdens of their profession. Participating in team-building exercises, engaging in regular brainstorming sessions, and fostering positive interactions with colleagues are highlighted as effective strategies to prevent isolation and burnout among teachers (Tasis, 2014). Social support systems play a crucial role in helping teachers regulate their emotions by providing avenues for expressing both positive and negative feelings. Expressing emotions through words helps teachers identify negative thoughts, evaluate reality, and

promote positive interpretations, a process known as cognitive reappraisal (Gross and John, 2003).

Subtheme 11.2. Stress Eating

Major of Teachers commonly turn to food as a coping mechanism for stress, a behavior observed in many professionals facing work-related challenges. Teacher 2, 3 and 5, for instance shared: " Food ang way ko para maovercome ko yung stress" ("Food is really my way to overcome stress.")... "Medyo magastos talaga ako, kasi yun yung way ko to destress" ("I'm quite extravagant because that's my way to destress.")

Although food may provide temporary relief, it can lead to long-term health issues and exacerbate stress levels. Teacher 1, for instance, mentions using coffee and eating out as ways to cope with stress, despite concerns about physical health repercussions such as acid reflux, saying: Coffee, kain sa labas yun yung way ko para maovercome ko ang stress sa work and emotional problem (Coffee, eating out is my way to overcome stress from work and emotional problems). It is crucial for teachers to explore healthier coping mechanisms such as exercise, meditation, or seeking support from trusted individuals to manage stress effectively and maintain overall well-being.

Subtheme 11.3. Catharsis

Catharsis, a process of releasing negative emotions often through crying, is a common strategy for teachers to regulate their emotions and alleviate emotional burdens. Crying serves as a healthy expression of pent-up feelings and helps teachers regain a sense of balance amid challenging circumstances. Teacher 1 said, Iiyak talaga, pag nailabas ko na okay na ako (I'm really going to cry, when I get it out I'm okay). Similar to teacher 5 who shared "when I cried that he was going to be gone, that was my way (pag naiyak ko na mawawala na sya, yun yung way ko). It is also an outlet to express negative feelings according to teacher 3 and 4 saying that, "Crying is my way to express my bad feelings more (Pag iyak yung way ko para mas maexpress ko pa yung bad feelings)

Although catharsis can provide relief from emotional overload, it is important for teachers to recognize that it is not a substitute for professional intervention for deeper emotional issues. Seeking resources like counseling, therapy, or support groups can offer long-term solutions for teachers struggling with emotional distress or mental health issues. Access to professional interventions, as noted in the current study, can significantly contribute to the emotional well-being of teachers.

1.4 Spiritual Well-being

Table showed that teachers perceived their spiritual well being positively, amidst internal struggle of inconsistent piety during this new normal and trying to make time for spiritual practices was seen as problem focused coping employed by teachers.

Table 7. *Personal View, Challenges and Coping Mechanisms developed supporting Spiritual well-being.*

Sample Verbatim	Codes	Sub-themes	Major themes
Personal View			
<i>"Kaya nga siguro nakakasurvive padin, di pa naman din ganon kahirap, though madaming loans, I think, kinakaya because of God. God provides, parang pag kinompare ang life namin sa buhay, may mas worst pa samin. Nakakaya padin kahit na may financial struggles." (Maybe that's why I'm still able to survive, it's not that difficult, although I have a lot of loans, I think I can handle it because of God. God provides, it seems like when our life is compared to life, there is something worse than us. It can be done even if there are financial struggles.)- (T5)</i>	Believing that God is there to help Consolation in Suffering Hope in Troubles	God's presence amid challenges	Positive Perception on Spirituality
<i>Yung paniniwala na malalampasan mo din ang lahat, kahit mabigat na, malalampasan mo din ang lahat, basta magtivala ka lang sa kanya." ("It's the belief that you can get through everything, even if it's hard, you can get through everything, just trust him.") (T4)</i>	Asking Guidance in Adversity Finding meaning to situations through faith	Finding meaning through Faithfulness	
<i>"Prayer is my way of meditation, talking to yourself, introspection, trying to process your feeling." (T3)</i>			
Challenges			
<i>"When I am okay, I neglect God in prayer, pag may problema doon ako mas lumalapit sa kanya, (When I am okay, I neglect God in prayer ("When there's a problem, that's when I tend to get closer to Him.") (T7)</i>	Lack of consistency in attending religious obligations Lost of prayer routine Forgetting about spiritual practices	Inconsistent Piety	Challenged by Inconsistent Piety
<i>"Hindi ako every Sunday nakakapagsimba, dasal lang (I don't go to church every Sunday, I just pray)." (T2)</i>			

Coping Mechanism

I am trying to recommit myself in going to mass and consistent prayers. Minsan di ako nakakaattend kasi gusto ko kasama family." (I am trying to recommit myself in going to mass and consistent prayers. Sometimes I can't attend because I want to be with my family.) (T3 similar to T1 & T2)

Going to Chapel in times of problems
Attending the mass when not busy
Allot time in prayers

Making time to nurture spirituality

Making time to nurture spirituality as coping

THEME 12: Positive Perception on Spirituality

Teachers often find strength in spirituality, turning to their faith for resilience in the face of challenges. They see their work as a calling with purpose and significance, finding comfort in the belief of a God or the Divine being guiding them through their struggles. This connection between spirituality and teaching shapes educators' perspectives and approaches in their professional and personal endeavors.

Subtheme 12.1. Recognizing God's Presence

Teachers' beliefs in transcendence, associated with the divine or God, have a direct connection to their faith and religious experiences. Many teachers have experienced an increase in faith during crises, observing how God provides in those times. For example, teacher 5 reflected on surviving the pandemic and financial struggles, attributing their resilience to God's intervention and provision saying that, "Maybe that's why I'm still able to survive, it's not that difficult, although I have a lot of loans, I think I can handle it because of God. God provides, it seems like when our life is compared to other people's lives, there is something worse than us. It can be done even if there are financial struggles". Another teacher found solace in communicating with God during emotional difficulties, experiencing unexpected blessings beyond their expectations. This highlights how teachers associate positive occurrences in their lives with God's work, fostering positive attitudes in challenging times.

Moreover, teachers acknowledge their spirituality by recognizing God's presence consistently, which gives them courage and a positive outlook on problems. Venting out concerns to God through personal prayer is seen as a source of comfort and support. Such reflections align with Fides Del Castillo's (2021) assertion that spiritual beliefs and practices serve as natural coping mechanisms during life's challenges, fostering positive psychological states of peace, healing, contentment, hope, and joy

Subtheme 12.2 Finding Meaning through Faithfulness

Teachers are aware how they lean on faith to find meaning everytime there is a problem, like for teacher 7 who said that "When I have a problem, that's when I become more religious, I visit the chapel, I talk and ask why. Why do I feel this way? When I am okay, I neglect".

They tend to seek God in their everyday experiences and through spiritual practices even when not actively participating in religious gatherings. This is evident to teacher 3 saying that "those in the bible, or learnings from mass and personal beliefs, are the beliefs that really gets me through in life". They turn to communication with God to make sense of life events, especially during periods of crisis. Through prayer and reflection, teachers find guidance and strength in their religious beliefs, which help them navigate challenges with hope and trust. This approach aligns with research by Pargament (1998) and Koenig (2021), suggesting that spirituality and religiosity positively impact coping mechanisms, leading to increased emotional well-being and decreased mental health issues.

During personal struggles, such as those experienced during the pandemic, teachers find solace and liberation in their connection with God. Teacher 6 view this saying that, "I just believe in God that I will be put in the place where I will grow more. I lost my job before and after that I gained a new one. God never neglected me. I have NOT been abandoned" Prayer becomes a vital means of expression and processing of emotions, alleviating negative feelings and fostering a sense of peace especially in solemn prayer. The act of sharing burdens with God through prayer provides comfort and relief, allowing teachers to express their true selves authentically. This practice is supported by research emphasizing the importance of a strong relationship with God in coping with life challenges and processing emotions.

Overall, teachers' experiences demonstrate the significant role of spirituality and faith in navigating crises, finding meaning in difficult situations, and fostering inner peace. Their reliance on God for guidance, strength, and support reflects a deep connection to their beliefs and highlights the positive impact of spirituality on well-being.

THEME 13: Challenged by Inconsistent Piety

Observing spiritual practices can be a challenging endeavor for teachers who struggle with inconsistent piety. Teacher 6 candidly shared, "I am Catholic, but I don't often go to mass every Sunday. However, in prayer, I establish my spiritual strength with God." Similarly, as a faithful Catholic, teacher 7 acknowledged a lack of depth in their faith by stating, "I am a faithful Catholic, but not deeply devoted." They also recognized that in times of ease and contentment, neglecting prayer can be easy and shared, "When I am okay, I neglect God in prayer; but when faced with problems, that's when I draw closer to Him."

During moments of struggle, teachers find solace and guidance through prayer, strengthening their spiritual connection with God. While some, like teachers 2, 1, and 4, may not attend mass regularly, they emphasize the importance of prayer in nurturing their relationship with the divine.

In conclusion, despite the challenges of inconsistent piety, prayer remains a powerful tool for teachers to navigate the balance between religious obligations and personal devotion. Even if they do not attend church every Sunday or see themselves as deeply devout, prayer stands as the cornerstone of their spiritual strength, fostering a profound connection with God. Maintaining a consistent commitment to spiritual practices poses a challenge but is crucial for spiritual well-being.

THEME 14: Making time to nurture spirituality as coping

Maintaining a sense of spiritual well-being is crucial for teachers, who often lead busy lives. Consistency and commitment to spiritual practices can be a lifeline, offering teachers a way to cope with the demands of their profession while fostering personal growth. Prioritizing spiritual activities in daily routines can help teachers achieve equilibrium and inner peace, nurturing their overall well-being.

Despite the challenges posed by demanding schedules, many teachers strive to make time for spiritual practices. They understand that connecting with their spirituality goes beyond mere religious rituals. Even in the absence of formal services, teachers carve out moments for prayer and reflection, as noted by teachers 1 and 2 saying that “When I have a problem, through prayer, I can express it to God.. I feel relieved. By incorporating these practices into their daily lives, both at school and at home, teachers aim to establish a sense of regularity and dedication, which ultimately enhances their spiritual health.

In addition to fostering spiritual well-being, committing to consistent practices also serves as a valuable coping mechanism for teachers. The stresses and strains of their profession can take a toll, leaving educators feeling overwhelmed and depleted. Engaging in spiritual activities like prayer offers teachers a sanctuary from work pressures, allowing them to rejuvenate and reconnect with themselves on a profound level. This is evident in the statement of teacher 5 who said, “I can go to church every Sunday, with God I can share burdens through prayer. There are times when I cry to God, I just say my problem”. Whether through meditation, yoga, or acts of kindness, these practices provide teachers with solace and tranquility, equipping them with the resilience needed to navigate their challenges with grace.

Integrating these spiritual practices into daily routines empowers teachers to attain a sense of harmony and tranquility, even amidst their bustling schedules. These rituals not only enhance their overall well-being but also act as effective coping mechanisms, equipping teachers to face the trials of their profession with renewed strength and optimism (Prasanna, G.S, & Palanivelu R., 2022).

1.5. Social well-being

The table below showed how teachers positively view their social well-being, amidst internal struggles experienced and challenges where they Seek social support as coping in those moments.

Table 8. *Personal View, Challenges and Coping Mechanisms developed supporting Social well-being.*

Sample Verbatim	Codes	Sub-themes	Major themes
Personal View			
<p>Ngayong full face- to- face, may nakakausap personal, lalo na pag stress ka.” (Now full face- to- face, there is someone to talk to personally, especially when you are stressed.”). (T4)</p> <p>“Natutunan ko ang pakikisama, kasi kahit nag tatrabaho ka kailangan makisama, lalo na lahat may pinagdaan nung pandemic, ” (I learned to get along, because even if you work, especially everyone has been through the pandemic”). (T6)</p>	<p>Friendliness and social relationship Positive feeling towards student and parent interaction</p>	<p>Forging positive relationships</p>	
<p>“Parang nabawasan ang pagiging sensitive naming mag-asawa silmula ng face-to- face, may nakakausap nang ibang tao. although my risk na iba ang sinasabi nila, in terms of trust.” (It seems that the sensitivity of my husband and I has deduced since face-to-face, we are talking to other people now. Although my risk is that they say otherwise, in terms of trust”). (T2)</p>	<p>Sharing with reservations Change of approach in interacting with students</p>	<p>Establishing trust in relationships</p>	<p>Positive Perception on Social wellbeing</p>
<p>“Yung iba hindi confident na mag share sa officials or counselors, we just talk with each other.” (“Others are not confident in sharing information with officials or counselors, but rather, they engage in conversations.”) (T3)</p>	<p>Seeking sympathy, validation and comfort</p>		

Challenges

<p><i>"Mas napapagod talaga ung makakasalamuha mo mga bata tapos yung mga concern, about sa kanila." ("It is really more tiring to interact with children than the concerns, about them"). (T4)</i></p>	<p>Exhaustion to engage with people adjustment to physical strain in socialization</p>	<p>Exhaustion and strain</p>	<p>Internal challenges on socialization</p>
<p><i>Before the pandemic, there was a time for socialization or we call it cloverleaf. We use that for games, picnic etc. Now, there is not much. Maybe it's because it's a bit busy, as there are a lot of adjustments during face-to-face." (T7)</i></p>	<p>No time to engage with friends inside and outside school lack of time talking with colleagues</p>	<p>Lack of time to Socialize</p>	

Coping Mechanism

<p><i>"Dahil nakapagod, humihingi ako ng tulong sa ka coteachers ko, sa counselors na mas kayang ihandle ang concerns ng mga bata" (Because it's tiring, I am asking for help from my co-teachers and counselors who are more capable of handling the children's concerns). (T4)</i></p>	<p>Finding strength through friendship discussing about school concerns and ask for help Participation and collaboration in activities</p>	<p>Seeking social support</p>	<p>Seeking social support as coping</p>
<p><i>"Nakikipag-usap ako sa mga ka coteachers, among other ways para mamanahe ko ang class ng maayos, kukuha ng ideas sa kanila kasi weakness ko talaga ang classroom management" ("I'm collaborating with coteachers to improve classroom management and share ideas with them to make the class more enjoyable"). (T5)</i></p>			

THEME 15: Positive Perception on Social wellbeing

Teachers prioritize their social well-being by emphasizing the cultivation of positive relationships and trust within their professional interactions. This includes fostering strong bonds between students and teachers, which are essential for creating a supportive and conducive learning environment.

Subtheme 15.1 Establishing trust in relationships

During the pandemic, social interactions were disrupted by concerns about health and safety, leading to increased social isolation and reliance on digital connections to mitigate the spread of COVID-19. As educators transitioned back to face-to-face interactions, establishing trust and rapport with colleagues became a significant challenge. Teacher 3 reflected on this transition, noting a decrease in confidence among colleagues in seeking support from officials or counselors, opting instead for conversations with each other. Similarly, Teacher 2 observed changes in behavior within their household, as the sensitivity between family members decreased with the resumption of face-to-face interactions.

Despite these challenges, efforts to open up and communicate were evident, although tempered by concerns about confidentiality. Socializing with colleagues served as a coping mechanism for many educators, providing comfort and validation during stressful times. Seeking validation of feelings and sympathy from peers offered a sense of relief and understanding, as shared by Teacher 4 and Teacher 1. Furthermore, the adjustment to new learning modalities facilitated collaboration and social relations both within and outside of the workplace.

In addition to supporting one another, teachers also adapted their teaching strategies to support students' learning amidst changes in learning modalities. This involved adopting more interactive and collaborative approaches in face-to-face instruction, as highlighted by Teacher 6 and Teacher 7. Such interactions were beneficial for both teachers and students, with students feeling more motivated to learn independently when they perceived autonomy support from their teachers, as suggested by Tomislava, Vidić., Marina, Đuranović., and Irena, Klasnic. (2023). Similarly, Robinson, C.D. (2022) emphasized the importance of teachers' motivational beliefs in fostering positive relationships with students, leading to more positive interactions and outcomes.

Subtheme 15.2 Forging positive relationships

Teachers expressed their appreciation for engagement and interaction, recognizing the potential adjustments to daily encounters with colleagues and others. For example, Teacher 4 highlighted the value of personal communication as a tool for managing stress, stating, "Now full face to face, there is someone to talk to personally, especially when you are stressed". Similarly, Teacher 3 noted the increased wellness resulting from social interaction with colleagues, despite the challenges of the pandemic, emphasizing the importance of

having someone to talk to during times of distress. Teacher 7 echoed this sentiment, stating, "I feel good when I go to the faculty room and talk with other teachers, that is the evidence that I feel okay", indicating that socialization with colleagues positively impacts mood and well-being.

Creating a friendly and welcoming atmosphere in the workplace was seen as crucial after a prolonged period of remote work. Teacher 6 emphasized the importance of socialization, especially in light of shared experiences during the pandemic, stating, "I learned to get along because everyone has been through the pandemic, you can't think that you are the only one who has gone through it". Similarly, Teacher 7 highlighted the significance of a positive work environment, stating, "The working environment is easier when you have established opportunities for acquaintance and making friends", the kind of atmosphere that teacher 7 envisions having". However, challenges such as increased workload and compassion fatigue from addressing students' concerns hindered some teachers' ability to fully engage with students (Pabillore et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2023).

Despite these challenges, Teacher 2 expressed positive feelings about interacting with students, viewing it as a form of rest from administrative tasks. Fostering a sense of community and support within the educational setting was recognized as essential for resilience and survival during difficult times (Kachchhap & Horo, 2021). Constructive criticism within supportive relationships helped maintain collaboration and support among teachers, facilitating personal growth and improvement. Communication of feelings within social groups, such as friends and colleagues, was found to be beneficial for teachers' mental and emotional health, reducing negative feelings and providing validation through sympathy (Monninger et al., 2023). This underscores the importance of real-life social interactions in enhancing mood and well-being, as online interactions may not fully compensate for their absence.

THEME 16: Internal challenges on socialization

One challenge impacting the social well-being of teachers is the exhaustion and strain experienced in student interactions. Managing the varied behavior and concerns of students can be taxing, as highlighted by Teacher 4, who expressed, "It is really more tiring to interact with children than the concerns about them". This suggests that the adjustment to students' learning experiences has led to a variety of concerns that educators must address, with changes in student behavior possibly stemming from socio-emotional adjustments due to the shift in learning modalities.

Despite these challenges, teachers continue to prioritize providing a safe and supportive learning environment for their students through social and professional interaction. This commitment demands significant effort and dedication, which can result in exhaustion and strain. However, with appropriate support and resources, educators can overcome these challenges and positively impact their students' lives. It is essential for teachers to prioritize their well-being and seek assistance when necessary to ensure they can continue delivering the best possible education (Dayagbil et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the lack of time due to work and other priorities has limited opportunities for socialization among teachers. Teacher 7 noted the shift in socialization practices, lamenting the decrease in time for activities like games and picnics due to busyness and adjustments to face-to-face interactions. They also highlighted the fragmentation of social groups, emphasizing the importance of unity to avoid division among colleagues as narrated by teacher 7 saying that: Before the pandemic, there was socialization, like Cloverleaf, which we used for games, picnics, etc. Nowadays, there isn't much. Perhaps it's because we're a bit busy, adjusting to face-to-face interactions again... In terms of socialization, it would be better if there were just one group. Because it seems like there's division. Especially in terms of population, it can't be avoided if there are groups.

This showed that lack of time due to work and other priorities limits the socialization along with the change in demands of schedule during the transition to full face to face interactions.

THEME 17: Seeking social support as coping

According to Kachchhap and Horo (2021), the attachment of teachers to their work groups is crucial for improved social interaction. This bond can yield positive attitudes and propel a safe and conducive educational environment forward. Teachers are often expected to work in teams, which can improve the teaching and learning process. Teacher 4 expressed this willingness to collaborate by stating, "Dahil nakakapagod, humihingi ako ng tulong sa ka coteachers ko, sa counselors na mas kayang ihandle ang concerns ng mga bata" (Because it's tiring, I am asking for help from my co-teachers and counselors who are more capable of handling the children's concerns). This means that collaborative efforts, such as learning how to personally communicate their concerns and seek help in the right approach, can lessen the weight of tasks and empower teachers to buy into a shared vision, engage in constant improvement, and extend peer support.

This is evident to teachers citing the statement of Teacher 5 saying that, "Nakikipag-usap ako sa mga ka coteachers, among other ways para mamange ko ang class ng maayos, kukuha ng ideas sa kanila kasi weakness ko talaga ang classroom management" ("I'm collaborating with coteachers to improve classroom management and share ideas with them to make the class more enjoyable". It emphasized the need for peer support and collaboration, stating that transitioning to face-to-face interactions helped them deal with challenges related to student socio-emotional behavior and approach strategy,

In conclusion, academic heads are called upon to foster a supportive atmosphere that is less divisive and appreciates teacher efforts, potentially improving the teaching and learning process. This highlights the direct contribution of collaboration in the workplace to the

social well-being of teachers and the promotion of a culture of understanding with colleagues, fostering support in resolving concerns and issues at hand.

1.6. Intellectual well-being

The table below showed that teachers perceive their Intellectual well-being positively, amidst the struggles of learning stagnation due to pandemic . Teachers cope through willingness to learn and ask questions or support from colleagues, most especially.

Table 9. *Personal View, Challenges and Coping Mechanisms developed supporting Intellectual well-being.*

Sample Verbatim	Codes	Sub-themes	Major themes
Personal View			
<p>“Nandun yung negative comments, I have to process them if i did wrong.” (Negative comments are there and you have to process if you did wrong). (T3)</p>	<p>Openness to feedback and comments Sensitivity to feedback and comments Embracing new perspective</p>	<p>Openness to Feedback</p>	
<p>“May mga times din an nakakatulong, nakakakuha ako ng ideas sa iba, natututo sa isat isa.” (There are also times it helps, I get ideas from others, and learn from each other). (T5)</p>			
<p>“I taught myself to be self-reliant. I am trying to process my own feelings. Pero pag di na talaga kaya I share din sa mom ko, husband or some friends (I taught myself to be self-reliant. I try to process my own feelings. But when I really can't, I also share with my mom, husband or some friends). (T3)</p>	<p>Relying on one’s capability to resolve the problem</p>	<p>Self-reliance</p>	<p>Positive Perception on Intellectual wellbeing</p>
<p>“Kailangan mag desisyon ako on my own, ways, kumakalma muna ako tinitignan ko ang possible sides, I will have my own decision, magtatanong ako to validate at tama ang naiisip ko. Actually ngayon, mas careful ako sa mga desisyon na gagawin ko, kasi tumatanda na, riskuy na kasi ang magtry on my end.” (I have to make a decision on my own, ways, I calm down first, I look at the possible sides, I will have my own decision, I will ask questions to validate and what I think is right. Actually now, I'm more careful in the decisions I make, because I'm getting older, it's risky to try on my end). (T6)</p>	<p>Reflective Practice Validating decision through peers</p>	<p>Discernment</p>	
Challenge			
<p>“I feel stagnant, kasi kung ano tinuro ko last year, same discussion this year. So parang for me, I need to learn something and do more. Para marevive yung first year of teaching ko. I'm not satisfied with my content.” (No, I feel stagnant, kasi kung ano tinuro ko last year, same discussion this year. So parang for me, I need to learn something and do more. Para marevive yung first year of teaching ko. I'm not satisfied with my content). (T3)</p>	<p>Fewer intellectual challenges Not applying previous learnings Similar teaching loads and tasks</p>	<p>Learning Stagnation</p>	<p>Challenge of Learning Stagnation</p>
Coping Mechanisms			
<p>“I need to learn more ways pa paano mahandle ang mga students, matutunan ko pa new strategies lalo na sa mga approaches sa classroom.” (I need to learn more ways to handle students, I need to learn new strategies especially in classroom approaches). (T7)</p>	<p>Willingness to enroll for further study Suggesting seminars and skill building activities</p>	<p>wanting to learn again</p>	<p>Problem-focused coping with intellectual well being</p>
<p>“Willing akong mag-aral ulit para matuto pa ng mga new approaches and strategies.” (I am willing to study again to learn new approaches and strategies.”) (T2 & T4)</p>			
<p>“Madalas akong humingi ng tulong sa co teachers lalo na pag hindi ko alam ang isang bagay.” (I often ask co teachers for help especially when I don't know something). (T1 and T3)</p>	<p>curiosity on things willingness to learn and discover more by asking</p>	<p>asking questions</p>	

THEME 18: Positive Perception on Intellectual wellbeing

The teachers expressed a positive outlook on intellectual well-being, emphasizing openness to feedback, striving for professional growth, self-reliance, and discernment as common themes in their responses. This theme demonstrate how the new normal has

facilitated their intellectual growth and challenged them.

Openness to criticism is vital for teachers' intellectual well-being and classroom effectiveness (Bahri, S., Situmorang, B., Darwin, D, 2022). The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers emphasize the importance of professional engagement, which includes accepting and giving feedback for improvement (Llego, 2019). Teachers exhibit varied responses to feedback. Some, like Teacher 3 and Teacher 1, view negative comments as opportunities for self-reflection and improvement saying that, “dati very fragile ako, I learned na pag sinabihan, makinig at you have to change, positive na ako sa mga comments and criticism. (I used to be very fragile, I learned that when I was told, listen and you have to change, I am now positive about comments and criticism). Here teachers value feedback from close relationships, seeing it as authentic and helpful. However, others, such as Teacher 7, admit to feeling emotionally sensitive to corrections, which can lead to questioning their abilities, saying that, “Kapag nacorrect naman doon ako nasasaktan, I question my capabilities, tama ba ang ginawa kpo. Mas dinidibid ko ang ginawa ko, mas nasaktan ako doon. (When I get corrected, I get hurt, I question my capabilities, is what I did right ?. The more I regret what I did, the more it hurt me)” which shows opportunity and commitment to grow and improve.. The manner and source of feedback play a significant role in how it is received. Constructive feedback is more likely to be accepted than feedback perceived as a personal attack. Despite challenges, teachers express a willingness to embrace new perspectives for self-growth, learning from each other in the process (Bahri, S., Situmorang, B., Darwin, D, 2022).

On the other hand, Teacher 3 emphasized the importance of self-reliance, stating, "I taught myself to be self-reliant. I try to process my own feelings. But when I really can't, I also share with my mom, husband or some friends." This reflects her belief in resolving manageable problems independently while being open to seeking help when necessary. Similarly, Teacher 5 expressed a nuanced approach, mentioning, "Depending on the problem, there are others that I want to keep to myself.. I don't like sharing my problems, some are resolved, others are not." This suggests a selective process of problem-sharing, highlighting the value of self-reliance while acknowledging the potential benefits of seeking assistance. These insights align with the understanding that self-reliance empowers individuals to manage challenges autonomously while also recognizing the role of social support when needed. It resonates with the findings of Hadbaatar, B. & Magsar, R., (2021), which observed that teachers demonstrate self-reliance in problem-solving while also engaging in collaborative approaches to generate diverse solutions.

In terms of decision making, Authenticity is crucial for teachers, involving self-reflection and validation. Teachers like Teacher 3 and Teacher 7 prioritize personal analysis before action, with Teacher 7 attributing this to introversion. Teacher 5 terms this process "retrospection," allowing for identification of strengths and weaknesses. Validation, as per Teacher 6, is essential for confirming decisions, seeking external perspectives to affirm authenticity. In conclusion, authenticity hinges on self-reflection and validation, guiding teachers to make informed decisions aligned with their values and seeking external confirmation when necessary.

THEME 19: Challenge of Learning Stagnation

The pandemic has been an educator in its own right, prompting teachers to adapt and enhance their skills, as Teacher 1 attests: "I discovered something during the pandemic, I became more tech-savvy." However, amidst the limited face-to-face interactions, Teacher 1 notes a decline in the nurturing of traditional skills: "Now, it feels like I'm not applying anything. The skills I once had are no longer relevant. It's because there are too many employees, and certain tasks are delegated elsewhere." This dilemma reflects a missed opportunity for growth, as teachers struggle to showcase their existing skills in the current landscape. On the other hand, Teacher 3 echoes this sentiment, expressing dissatisfaction with the lack of progression: "I feel stagnant. What I taught last year is the same discussion this year. I need to learn and do more to revive the excitement of my first year of teaching. I'm not satisfied with my content." This frustration stems from a lack of challenge and professional development opportunities.

Teacher 4 concurs, stating, "For me, there's been no change or improvement; it's all the same." This stagnation is attributed to the absence of new learning experiences and skill development opportunities at work.

Teacher 7 laments the hindrance caused by the pandemic on their professional growth: "Since face-to-face interactions have ceased, I've reverted to my old routines. I need to focus on preparing more lessons and activities. There's been no progress; I'm just retracing my steps." This regression is compounded by limited access to resources, time constraints, and inadequate institutional support.

Overall, the pandemic-induced learning stagnation poses significant challenges for teachers, impeding their professional development and diminishing their enthusiasm for the profession.

THEME 20: Problem-focused coping with intellectual well being

The pandemic has necessitated a shift in teaching methods, compelling educators and students to utilize online platforms and self-learning due to school closures. This transition has encouraged teachers like Teacher 7 to pursue self-learning to improve lesson content and develop strategies for managing student behavior. Various approaches, such as attending seminars and conducting research, facilitate this pursuit, as noted by Teacher 3. Research by Louws et al. (2017) confirms that teachers determine their own learning needs, with early-career teachers showing a preference for broader learning compared to mid-career peers focused on classroom management.

Despite the challenges of face-to-face teaching, educators must continue self-learning to adapt and inspire lifelong learning in students, as recommended by Smith and Klerk (2022). Active learning and collaboration among teachers, as evidenced by their reliance on

colleagues and friends for assistance and learning opportunities, are crucial for intellectual well-being and skill improvement. Seeking clarification through questioning fosters effective learning, as observed by Teacher 2, who learns from students' opinions and answers, particularly from the Gen Z cohort. Prioritizing collaboration and inquiry empowers teachers to develop the skills and knowledge necessary for their educational journey.

1.7. Physical well-being

This table showed that teachers mostly have negative perceptions on Physical well-being, relative to internal struggles identified since the transition to full face to face. Teachers cope with these through healthy lifestyle choices and utilization of healthcare benefits.

Table 10. *Personal View, Challenges and Coping Mechanisms developed supporting Physical well-being.*

Sample Verbatim	Codes	Sub-themes	Major themes
Personal View			
<p>“Mas haggard, mas stressful, physically drained compared nung dating online lang, feeling ko kulang na exercise, kulang sa healthy food, di nanakakaluto. I don't feel healthy and glowing.” (More haggard, more stressful, physically drained compared to when it was only online. I feel like I don't exercise enough, I don't eat healthy food, I can't cook. I don't feel healthy and glowing). (T5)</p>	Signs of body fatigue. workload and physical exhaustion	physical strain and fatigue	Negative Perception on Physical wellbeing
<p>I used to walk at night after work. Di ko na sya magawa ngayon kasi naaffectuhan ang health ko, medyo mataas ang uric acid ko.” (Used to walk at night after work. I can't do it now because my health is affected, my uric acid is quite high). (T7)</p>	Seeking adequate rest and recovery to combat fatigue. Finding time to move and exercise	Physical health concerns	
<p>“Dati nakakapag gym, ngayon hindi na kasi wala nang time.” (I used to go to the gym, but now I don't because I don't have time). (T1)</p>	Prioritizing self-care activities to address physical health concerns.		
Challenges			
<p>“Super napupuyat sa sobrang busy sa bahay at school.” (I lack sleep since I have super busy work at home and school). (T5)</p>			
<p>“Tulog ko, nag mamadaling araw ako, yung time management wala masyado, when I work, I work regardless of the time, kasi I love what I am doing (I sleep, I rush through the day, there is not much time management, when I work, I work regardless of the time, because I love what I am doing)”. (T6)</p>	Lack of sleep due to too much responsibility Irregular sleeping patterns	Sleep Deprivation	
<p>“May nararamdaman ako, hindi ko lang pinapacheck natatakot ako ano madiscover ko.” (If I have a feeling, I just don't check it because I'm afraid of what I might discover). (T1)</p>	Anxiety about the results of laboratory tests Fear from check up to Doctors	Fearful prognosis	Internal Challenge on physical wellbeing
<p>Natatakot ako mag patingin nung nararamdaman ko minsan, ayokong may malaman ako (I'm afraid to look when I feel sometimes, I don't want to know anything). (T2)</p>			
<p>“Pagkain din minsan napapasobra.” (Food is sometimes too much.”) (T4)</p>	Improper eating routine or habits		
<p>“Malakas akong kumain, yun yung way ko para mareduce ang stress, medyo tumaba na nga ako, nag overeat ako.” (I eat a lot, that's my way to reduce stress, I've gained a little weight, I overeat). (T5)</p>	Not eating and buying healthy and nutritious food Eating alot Poor eating lifestyle	Poor Eating Habits	
Coping Mechanisms			

"Less nalang mga bawal para di tumaas ang cholesterol at uric, disiplina lang." (I used to lessen food allotment so that cholesterol and uric don't increase, just discipline.) (T4)

"Pagkain, dapat portion padin, pwede kumain sa labas wag lang sobra, pwede sa karne, wag lang sobra at balanse lang dapat. Isip talaga, mind over matter." (Food, should be portioned, you can eat outside, just don't eat too much, you can eat meat, just don't eat too much and it should be balanced. Really mind, mind over matter). (T1)

"May insurance, yun ang isa sa inaasahan ko and also maxicare pag may concern sa health." (There is insurance, that's one of my expectations and also maxicare when there are health concerns). (T3)

"Nagagamit naman ang Maxicare (hmo) pag annual check up (Maxicare (hmo) can be used for annual check up) (T1)

Embracing balance in work, rest, and play for a healthier lifestyle. Striving to do exercise and eat proper foods

Making healthy lifestyle choices

Coping from Physical health Problems

Use of health benefits like HMOs

Access to Health Care

THEME 21: Negative Perception on Physical wellbeing

The lack of attention to health habits, compounded by the transition to face-to-face classes, has significantly impacted teachers' physical well-being. Factors such as the school environment, seniority, and academic workload contribute to this strain. Prioritizing health and well-being is imperative to ensure teachers can perform optimally. Encouraging healthy habits, incorporating breaks into their routines, and fostering a supportive work environment are crucial steps in addressing this issue.

Despite the proven benefits of exercise, all teacher participants struggle to prioritize it due to their hectic schedules. This shift has led to concerns about a sedentary lifestyle among educators, with some expressing regret over their diminishing exercise routines. Efforts to incorporate physical activity, albeit sporadic, highlight the recognition of its importance among teachers.

The sedentary lifestyle prevalent among teachers poses significant health risks, including obesity, heart disease, and diabetes. Moreover, the transition to in-person classes may exacerbate existing health conditions, as evidenced by teachers experiencing increased uric acid levels and back pain triggered by prolonged standing.

To mitigate these challenges, schools must prioritize promoting physical activity among teachers by providing access to fitness facilities and wellness programs. Educating teachers on the importance of physical activity and the risks associated with a sedentary lifestyle is **also crucial**.

THEME 22: Internal Challenge on physical wellbeing

Teachers commonly struggle with sleep deprivation due to their demanding work schedules, often sacrificing sleep to meet their responsibilities. For example, one teacher mentioned, "I lack sleep since I have super busy work at home and school" (Teacher 5). This sentiment was echoed by another teacher who said, "When I work, I work regardless of the time, because I love what I am doing" (Teacher 6). This indicates that passion for teaching sometimes leads to neglecting one's own well-being. Additionally, the demands of work can hinder proper sleep, as expressed by Teacher 3, who stated, "Lack of sleep all the time, even working at night."

The lack of sleep can have negative consequences, including fatigue and moodiness, which can affect teachers' performance and overall health. Despite these challenges, many teachers continue to prioritize their work over their own well-being, as seen in Teacher 1 struggle to find time for relationships due to work obligations.

Similarly, poor eating habits among teachers pose health risks, such as obesity and fatigue. Some teachers resort to overeating as a coping mechanism for stress, as mentioned by Teacher 5, who said, "I eat a lot, that's my way to reduce stress." Unhealthy eating habits, combined with a sedentary lifestyle, contribute to poor physical health among teachers.

Furthermore, some teachers exhibit health anxiety, avoiding medical check-ups out of fear of discovering a serious illness. This fear may stem from financial or socio-emotional concerns, highlighting the need for greater awareness and support for teachers' mental health. To cope with these challenges and promote physical well-being, teachers employ various strategies such as mindful eating and intermittent fasting. By making healthier lifestyle choices and seeking medical care when needed, teachers can better manage their physical health and improve their overall well-being.

THEME 23: Coping from Physical health Problems

Despite the obstacles to physical health highlighted by the teachers, they demonstrate a mindful approach to managing the repercussions of poor diet and nutrition. Teachers have articulated their efforts to regulate their food intake to mitigate the onset and persistence of health issues, as evidenced by the following statements:

"Pagkain, dapat portion padin, pwede kumain sa labas wag lang sobra, pwede sa karne, wag lang sobra at balanse lang dapat. Isip talaga, mind over matter." (Food should be portioned, you can eat outside, just don't eat too much, you can eat meat, just don't eat too much and it should be balanced. Really mind, mind over matter) - Teacher 1

"Ngayon medyo nagbabawas ng kain para maiwasan pagtaas ng uric, nag iingat na din in terms sa pagkain." (Now I'm cutting down on food a bit to prevent uric acid from rising, he's also being careful in terms of food) Teacher 7

Furthermore, teachers adopt various strategies such as fasting to regulate blood sugar levels and enhance food digestion, alongside supplement intake and coffee consumption to boost energy levels, as expressed by teacher 3: "Intermittent fasting, they said it helps you lower your blood sugar, and helps your digestive system. Drinking supplements and coffee."

Additionally, despite the demands of their profession on physical health, teachers recognize the importance of accessing healthcare resources to address their well-being. Schools play a crucial role in supporting teachers' health through provisions such as Health Maintenance Organizations (HMOs) or health packages, as attested by teachers saying "Nagagamit naman ang Maxicare (HMO) pag annual check up." (Maxicare (HMO) can be used for annual check-up) -Teacher 1 "Ngagamit naman ang Maxicare, kahit namamaximize, still nakakatulong sya sa check-ups." (Maxicare can be used, even though it is maximized, it still helps with check-ups) - Teacher 7

Furthermore, teachers appreciate the availability of external healthcare resources, demonstrating a commitment to prioritizing their health despite challenges. For instance, teacher 5 acknowledges the importance of insurance coverage and access to Maxicare for addressing health concerns. The provision of healthcare benefits by schools is commendable, albeit socioeconomic factors such as income level and insurance coverage can influence a teacher's ability to afford and access medical care. In addition, schools offer support for sudden health concerns through onsite clinics, providing first aid and accommodations when needed, as affirmed by teacher 6 saying that, "The school is allowing us to use the facilities and we have the clinic to accommodate us." ... "Pag masama pakiramdam, nagclinic very accommodating naman saamin." (When feeling unwell, the clinic is very accommodating to us all)

These practices underscore the school's commitment to prioritizing teachers' health and recognizing it as a fundamental need and right, allowing educators to effectively manage their well-being and fulfill their professional responsibilities.

1.8. Environmental well-being

Table showed positive perceptions of teachers on Environmental well-being, amidst internal struggle of not prioritizing the environment since the transition to full face to face learning in new normal education. Teachers cope with this by striving to make care environment efforts.

Table 11. *Personal View, Challenges and Coping Mechanisms developed supporting Environmental well-being.*

Verbatim Sample	Codes	Sub-themes	Major themes
Personal View			
"Dahil papago bago ang weather, at sonrang init mas narerealized ko yung need talaga na pangalagaan na ang kalikasan." (T 7)	Awakened sense of care for environment	Care for Environment	
"aware ako na talagang need na natin mag conserve at pangalagaan ang environment para maiwasan mga sakuna." (T4)			
"Satisfied naman ako sa environment actually akakatulong nga, conducive yung place at hindi nakakastress." (I'm satisfied with the environment, actually it help me and it's conducive, it doesn't stress me out.) (T5)	Appreciating safety at work Appreciating greenery and relaxing environment	Safe work environment	Positive Perception on Environmental wellbeing
"Sa school gusto ko yung malawak at kahit papaano may puno maaliwalas, minsan naglalakad lakad ako at ineenjoy ko yung ambience." (I like to go to school and At least have a tree that is clear, sometimes I walk around and enjoy the ambience.) (T3 & T2)			
Challenges			
"Di ko na masyado nabibigyan ng panahon ang paglilinis." (I don't have much time to clean) (T6)	Lack of time to prioritize environmental initiatives	Environment Not a Priority	Environment Not a Priority
"Wala talaga masyadong initiative, parang hindi sya ang priority ko at the monent, madami pang mas urgent na iniisp." (There's really			

not much initiative, it doesn't seem like he's my priority at the moment, there's a lot more urgent things to prioritize). (T7)

Coping Mechanism

"Conscious ako pag may kalat itatapon sa tamang basurahan, ayoko din kasi ng magulo." (I am conscious that whenever there are garbage/mess, I usually put them in a proper bin. I want everything in proper). (T2)

"Practice claygo (Clean as you go) all the time." (T6 & T7)

"Minsan pag may time nag lilinis ako, nag dedeclutter ng mga gamit para mabawasan ang kalat." (Sometimes when I have time I usually clean and declutter, to reduce the mess/garbage). (T1)

Efforts to help take care the environment

Effort in taking care of environment

Effort in taking care of environment

THEME 24: Postive Perception on Environmental wellbeing

Teachers are keenly aware of the necessity to conserve and safeguard the environment to prevent calamities, as stated by teacher 1 saying, "Yes aware ako na talagang need na natin mag conserve at panaglagaan ang environment para maiwasan mga sakuna" (I'm aware that we really need to conserve and protect the environment to avoid disasters). They relate this awareness to personal encounters, such as witnessing rapid flooding and pollution. Additionally, they emphasize the significance of a safe and conducive work environment, expressing contentment with its cleanliness and atmosphere. They emphasize how workplace conditions affect their health and mental well-being: According to one of the participants, teacher 6 for instance agreed on statement: "cleanliness of the workplace contributes to my health para hindi magkasakit. positive people also bring peace to my mental health" (The cleanliness of the school contributes to my health so that I don't get sick. positive people also bring peace to my mental health). This underscores the interconnectedness of environmental consciousness, satisfaction with the work environment, and overall well-being.

THEME 25: Environment Not a Priority

One significant issue faced by teachers in terms cultivating their environmental wellbeing was the lack of prioritization on environmental initiatives within and beyond workplace. For teacher 3, and 1, they admitted the lack of effort in cleaning the house saying that, "wala na akong time mag linis e, dahil most of the time nasa school bihira nalang makapag linis sa bahay (I don't have time to clean up, because most of the time at school I rarely get to clean the house)" This is similar to Teacher 4 and 6 saying that, "Di ko na masyado nabibigyan ng panahon ang paglilinis(I don't have much time to clean) Additionally, Teacher 7 admitted that he lacked initiative as it is less important than current endeavors, saying that "Wala talaga masyadong initiative , parang hindi sya ang priority ko at the moment, madami pang mas urgent na iniisp (There's really not much initiative , it doesn't seem like he's my priority at the moment, there's a lot more urgent things to prioritize.) When environmental initiatives are not given the attention they deserve, teachers may find themselves struggling to create a conducive learning environment. The absence of proper waste management systems, inadequate access to green spaces, and a lack of emphasis on sustainability practices can all contribute to a decline in the overall wellbeing of teachers. These factors can lead to increased stress levels, reduced job satisfaction, and even physical health issues. It is important for a university to incorporate environmental wellness as part of the program by providing teachers with the necessary resources and training to implement sustainable practices in their classrooms, and creating a supportive environment that values and promotes environmental wellbeing. In doing so, we can ensure that teachers' lived experiences are enriched, leading to a positive impact on their overall wellbeing and the wellbeing of future generations.

THEME 26: Effort in taking care of environment

Teacher's sense of awareness allowed them to recognize and continue their existing efforts of taking care the environment. For teacher 3, "I always bring my own eco bag every time we go shopping, besides that it's more durable to avoid too much plastic." (sa pagtatapon ng basura sa tamang tapunan and I always bring my own eco bag every time na mamimili kami bukod sa mas matibay iyon para makaiwas sa sobrang daming plastic.) Similarly, other teachers shared initiatives to take care of the environment such as:

For teacher 6 and 7 practice claygo all the time.

For teacher 2: Conscious ako pag may kalat itatapon sa tamang basurahan, ayoko din kasi ng magulo (I am conscious that whenever there are garbage/mess, I usually put them in a proper bin. I want everything in proper) For teacher 1, Minsan pag may time nag lilinis ako, nag dedeclutter ng mga gamit para mabawasan ang kalat (Sometimes when I have time I usually clean and declutter, to reduced the mess/garbage. By incorporating these strategies into their daily habits, teachers can inspire and empower others specially the students to become responsible stewards of the environment, while nurturing their wellbeing and contribute to efforts in preserving and conserving our natural resources.

The Figure below shows the framework of the Psychosocial Support Services. To advance the focus on teacher well-being, the

challenges to well-being identified through the themes (outermost layer) were grouped and analyzed according to its specific dimension of well-being. The wheel represented 5 areas of improvement in Teachers' well-being (Third layer) giving focus on activities fit to the needs of the teacher. These are:

A. Career Development: It involves appreciation, skill, and knowledge enhancement, establishing of long or short-term career goals for professional growth and lifelong learning. (Activities such as: Capacity Building and Training on specific target skills/topics need like, Conflict Resolutions, Decision Making and New approaches and strategies in teaching and learning, Information Services (IS) on Self-Assessment Activities /Acknowledging strengths and weaknesses, Time management workshops, Professional Responsibilities and expectations on teacher, Seminar on Child behavior Interventions. Additionally, One-on-one peer coaching and Case Conferencing, Focus Group Discussion will encourage professional development. Assessment and planning for Increased coverage of Teacher's Benefits and Incentives).

B. Financial Literacy: It includes assessment of financial needs, mindful and wise financial planning, saving, and budgeting of financial resources. Activities such as Information Services (IS) on saving and investments, Recognizing needs and wants and the Emergent expenses, and Financial Literacy Assessment).

C. Positive Emotions: It centers on activities that foster understanding and expression of feelings and emotions and their proper management. Information Service (IS) are suggested such as stress and anxiety awareness and coping seminars, socio-emotional learning experiences, Practice of Gratitude Journaling, Self-care and affirmation Exercises, Mindfulness and Self-awareness exercises. It is also recommend creating Wellness rooms: Peace corners, provide teachers and staff with a designated space to promote and practice mindfulness, self-care, and reflection. Check-in, Counseling and Consultations must be offered.

D. Meaningful Connections: It includes activities that help teachers realize their purpose, and sense of meaning in relationships with Man, Nature, and the Transcendence (God). Activities to hone meaningful connection to the transcendence or God and nature will be helpful to find meaning and self-discovery, Initiatives such as; Encourage participation and plan for Spiritual activities such as Prayers, Masses and Other religious services, Incorporate prayer in school practices/activities. Volunteer to a church and charitable community activities, Observance of Basic sustainability and taking care of environment practices at school and home. Seminar on It is suggested to plan for specific activities to improve social Social skills and effective communication, Peer-Helping among teachers and quarterly socialization days: Providing opportunity for Engagements, Camaraderie and Community building.

E. Physical Health and Safety: It involves activities that promote proper nutrition, sleep, safety, and protection, and the overall physical health of the teachers. Wellness Activities like integration of healthy habits at school, exercise promotion and organizing workshop or Information service on balanced nutrition and ways for physical health care. A need for Regular check up and Infographics showing relationship of Physical wellbeing to other aspects of health will also encourage confidence and valuing on one's personal health.

Generally, this developed framework of psychosocial services serves as a guide in planning specific activities and interventions that address the challenges experienced by the teachers in terms of the various dimensions of well-being.

3. Implication of the study to Guidance and Counseling

The current study delves into the challenges faced by university teachers in unprecedented times, emphasizing the necessity for comprehensive support systems to aid them. Teachers have undergone immense stress due to various challenges impacting their overall well-being, making it imperative for guidance counselors to acknowledge and tackle these issues that directly influence teacher effectiveness in addressing students' emotional needs. Examining the eight dimensions of well-being among teachers in the new normal offers significant implications for reshaping how guidance and counseling are perceived and implemented in this altered educational landscape.

The study's findings intertwine teachers' personal perspectives, hurdles faced, and coping mechanisms for well-being within the broader school culture, hinting at extending the role of counselors to support teachers as well. By being champions of well-being, counselors can contribute to fostering a nurturing environment where both students and staff feel valued and supported. Prioritizing teachers' well-being, as evidenced by this study, can positively impact overall morale and productivity, not only in post-pandemic times but also during periods of crisis.

Focusing on the eight dimensions of well-being - physical, emotional, social, intellectual, occupational, environmental, financial, and spiritual - offers a holistic view that recognizes the multifaceted nature of well-being and necessitates attention to various aspects of life. Collaboration between counselors and teachers to design tailored initiatives that address teachers' unique needs not only enhances their well-being but also benefits the wider school community.

Insights from teachers on daily stressors and coping mechanisms can improve their resilience, as counselors equipped with knowledge of the eight dimensions of well-being can provide targeted support to alleviate stressors. Psychosocial support services highlighting self-care, stress reduction, and providing a safe space for teachers to express concerns are vital in enhancing overall teacher well-being, as highlighted in the study.

Incorporating the study's findings on well-being dimensions into guidance and counseling curricula can serve as a model for teachers

and students, fostering a culture of well-being and normalizing help-seeking behaviors. This approach can significantly improve resilience and wellness within the educational community, thereby enhancing overall well-being.

Moreover, the study underscores the importance of collaboration between educators, administrators, and mental health professionals like guidance counselors in creating a supportive working environment for teachers and a safe space for students. The evolving nature of teaching necessitates evidence-based plans focused on well-being, enabling counselors to make informed decisions and interventions that target specific needs effectively.

Therefore, by embracing the insights garnered from studying the eight dimensions of teacher well-being, guidance and counseling programs can evolve to better support teachers, ultimately contributing to their success and well-being in the ever-changing educational environment.

Figure 1.1. Psychosocial Support Services Development Wheel

2. Proposed Psychosocial Support Services

W.E.T.H.R.I.V.E

Wellness Empowered Educators: Total Health, Resilience, Inspiration, Vitality and Expressions

Rationale:

This proposal for psychosocial support services for teachers in the post-pandemic era is based on the recognition of the well-being of teachers and the significant challenges they have faced and continue to face as they navigate the new educational landscape post-COVID-19. Understanding the impact of the pandemic on teachers' overall health, the program aims to provide support for teachers' well-being as they confront new challenges in both their personal and professional lives. By creating a nurturing and supportive environment, the program aims to enhance teachers' resilience, reduce stress levels, and promote a positive work-life balance. Additionally, the program acknowledges the importance of equipping teachers with the necessary tools and resources to effectively adapt to the new normal in education, ensuring their continuous professional growth and development. Ultimately, the wellness program for teachers in the post-pandemic period is driven by the belief that prioritizing their well-being is essential for establishing a sustainable and thriving educational system.

Objectives

The psychosocial support services for teachers take a holistic approach that considers both psychological and social factors that impact an individual's overall well-being. This intervention is designed to promote holistic well-being in various aspects such as vocational, emotional, financial, social, spiritual, intellectual, physical, and environmental well-being to enhance personal growth, work performance, and life and job satisfaction. Through this program, teachers will have the opportunity to develop healthy habits, effectively manage stress, and improve their overall quality of life. Moreover, planning for services aim to establish a supportive and positive work environment that encourages collaboration, communication, and mutual respect among teachers. By achieving these objectives, the wellness program for teachers will not only benefit the teachers themselves but also the students they teach and the school community at large.

Conclusion

Several studies on wellbeing in the new normal focus on few groups, mostly with younger groups. This comprehensive examination of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on teachers' well-being covered eight distinct aspects: vocational, financial, emotional, spiritual, social, intellectual, physical, and environmental well-being. The study found that Teachers generally hold a positive perception of their vocational well-being, deriving satisfaction from their role, purpose, and the value of their work. However, they encounter challenges such as salary issues, workload, recognition, and work-life balance, both externally (e.g., workload, salary) and internally (e.g., doubts about abilities). Coping mechanisms include time management, seeking support from colleagues, and emotional compartmentalization.

Financially, the transition to in-person learning exacerbates financial pressures for teachers. Challenges include reduced income, difficulties in budgeting, and financial instability affecting other dimensions of well-being. Coping strategies involve saving money, budgeting, and occasionally relying on credit.

Emotional Well-being: In terms of emotional wellbeing, teachers prioritize emotional needs but face challenges such as anxiety, self-doubt, and frustration. Coping mechanisms include stress eating and emotional regulation, but there's a need for healthy habits and stress management tools.

In terms of spiritual well being, Teachers find meaning and peace in their spiritual beliefs, especially during crisis. Internal challenges include inconsistent piety, addressed through finding time for attending religious gathering and prayers which is considered problem-focused coping. However, Socially, the pandemic hampers socialization, but interactions with colleagues provide support. Teachers feel exhausted due to heavy workloads and time constraints but benefit from seeking support and engaging in dialogue. Additionally, in terms of intellectual well being, Teachers maintain a positive outlook on intellectual well-being but face obstacles in continuous learning. Challenges include demanding schedules, burnout, and limited resources, hindering professional development like further studies.

Physically, teachers perceive their physical health as low, attributed to strain, fatigue, and sedentary lifestyles. Challenges include sleep deprivation and poor eating habits, addressed through problem-focused coping strategies. On the other hand, teachers understand the importance of environmental conservation but struggle to prioritize it. Coping involves efforts in environmental conservation, but prioritizing other well-being aspects is crucial.

In response to these challenges, proposed Psychosocial Support Services presented ways to enhance teacher well-being by addressing the key areas identified through the findings namely: career development, financial literacy, emotional positivity, meaningful connections, and physical health and safety. Continuous improvement and adaptation on these aspects are necessary to meet evolving needs. To ensure the effectiveness of Psychosocial Support Services for teachers, institutions need to adapt and assess its effectiveness.

The researcher recommends to future researches on wellbeing, to not only limit the study on wellbeing to teachers but involve the staff of the school community to gain more insights on the phenomenon and alike. Before or after pandemic, teacher's wellbeing and interventions will remain relevant. Recruiting a diverse sample of teachers in different ways, representing different disciplines, teaching levels, and demographic backgrounds, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity. Gender could also be a factor that influences the challenge and possible coping supporting the wellbeing, thus, further study can focus on the role of gender and even socio-economic factors on the quality of wellbeing of teachers. Moreover, researchers should conduct further studies using different methods in specific groups or settings to understand well-being dimensions and effective techniques for teachers. Findings may lead to developing a tool to assess teachers' well-being. Quantitative data can help institutions gauge teacher well-being. Collaboration with university administrators, HR personnel, chaplains, and counselors is crucial. Universities and even other Institutions should align policies to enhance teacher well-being, job satisfaction, and productivity, ultimately promoting mental health in schools and supporting holistic teacher development.

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